

European Tourism Data Space

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D6.2 Dissemination, communication and exploitation report

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List of Acronyms

Abbreviation / acronym	Description
BDVA	Big Data Value Association
D.	Deliverable
C&D&E	Communication, Dissemination, and Exploitation
DG	Directorate General
DS4SSCC	Data Space for Sustainable and Smart Cities and Communities
DSSC	Data Spaces Support Centre
DMOs	Destination Management Organisation
ETDS	European Tourism Data Space
EU	European Union
HaDEA	European Health and Digital Executive Agency
IDSA	International Data Space Association
ICCA	International Congress and Convention Association
KER	Key Exploitable Results
KOM	Kick-off Meeting
KPI	Key Performance Indicator
M	Month
MOOC	Massive Open Online Cours
PTR	Project Technical Results
SAAS	Software as a service
SMEs	Small Medium Enterprises
WP	Work Package

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Executive Summary

This document is a deliverable submitted in the frame of the DEPLOYTOUR project, co-funded by the European Commission.

The DEPLOYTOUR - Deployment of a Trusted and Secure Common European Tourism Data Space - aims to create a unified European Tourism Data Space. By facilitating sovereign data sharing across borders and between the public and private sectors, the project will help enhance operational efficiency, enable new services to emerge, improve the user experience, stimulate innovation (including access to data for AI), and contribute to the digital and sustainable transition of the tourism sector.

This report summarises the Communication, Dissemination, and Exploitation (C&D&E) activities carried out during the first phase of the DEPLOYTOUR project.

It covers the period from October 1st, 2024, to August 31st, 2025. It presents the communication, dissemination, and exploitation plan, outlining the activities carried out, key results, findings, and outcomes achieved through outreach and awareness activities, as well as the exploitation strategy.

The project's C&D&E strategy is built around four core objectives: raising awareness among the identified stakeholders; informing and educating about data spaces, sovereignty, and their value for European tourism; engaging and mobilising stakeholders; and creating synergies through ecosystem updates and joint communication with complementary EU projects.

Over the first year, DEPLOYTOUR has successfully launched its awareness phase, establishing visibility and recognition. This phase has demonstrated positive outcomes, including increased follower engagement, participation in DEPLOYTOUR activities, website visitors, and newsletter subscriptions, among others. DEPLOYTOUR has also established itself as a leading authority in its field through participation in international, European, and national events, while fostering a dynamic ecosystem via webinars, media appearances, and invitations to high-profile conferences.

Moving forward, strong collaboration between WP6 and other work packages will be essential to highlight DEPLOYTOUR's added value, results, and impact, ensuring sustained stakeholder engagement and long-term adoption of the ETDS. By maintaining this strategic alignment, DEPLOYTOUR will continue to expand its influence, deepen stakeholder involvement, and solidify its role as a catalyst for innovation in European tourism.

The document highlights the actions undertaken by the project and the consortium partners, showcasing both general initiatives and specific contributions.

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1. Introduction

1.1 Purpose of the Document

This report summarises the Communication, Dissemination, and Exploitation activities carried out during the first phase of the DEPLOYTOUR project, from October 1st, 2024, to August 31st, 2025.

1.2 Structure of the Document

The document is organised as follows:

1. Executive Summary

A brief overview of the report's purpose, a summary of the main activities undertaken, and the overall impact of the actions implemented.

2. Communication dissemination and exploitation Plan

This section outlines the primary objectives of DEPLOYTOUR's communication and dissemination strategy, along with an assessment of the project's communication landscape to identify key opportunities and challenges.

This part also defines the content strategy, which forms the foundation of the Communication, Dissemination, and Exploitation Plan. The plan provides a concrete, detailed and actionable roadmap for executing WP6 activities, compiling both ongoing and planned actions to ensure proactive implementation, transparency, and alignment with DEPLOYTOUR's objectives.

In this chapter, the last section provides an overview of the target Audiences, key Messages and communication channels.

3. Activities carried out

This section details the activities conducted during the reporting period, as outlined in the Communication, Dissemination, and Exploitation Plan. It documents all communication efforts undertaken by DEPLOYTOUR and its consortium, including internal procedures established to ensure the effective implementation of WP6 across the project.

A particular emphasis is placed on communication channels, explaining their usage and impact on the project's visibility, supported by practical examples. The section also highlights events organised directly by DEPLOYTOUR, as well as those attended by partners.

Additionally, it showcases collaborative efforts with WP5, particularly in co-organising joint webinars to foster synergies with other data space initiatives.

Comprehensive tables in the annexes compile all events attended by DEPLOYTOUR partners, while other tables summarise publication materials, such as newsletters, articles, blogs, press releases, and podcasts, produced by DEPLOYTOUR and its partners.

Finally, the section includes a dedicated overview of media exposure, detailing local, national, and European coverage to illustrate the project's expanding visibility and outreach.

4. Results and impact metrics

This section presents the key performance indicators (KPIs) used to evaluate the impact of DEPLOYTOUR's communication and dissemination activities. It compiles comprehensive data and statistics, including social media engagement metrics, website traffic analytics, and newsletter performance, to assess the effectiveness and reach of the project's outreach efforts and analyse the strategy to make the necessary adjustments.

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5. Exploitation strategy

This section outlines the exploitation strategy, which will begin implementation from Month 12. It details the methodology, key phases, and tools that will be employed to ensure the effective and sustainable utilisation of DEPLOYTOUR's results.

6. Conclusion

This final part summarises the key findings, the importance of communication to the project's success, and final reflections.

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2. Communication, dissemination and exploitation plan

WP6's main objective is to effectively communicate the benefits of the common European tourism data space, as well as the specific results and outcomes of the project, to a wide range of stakeholders, including policymakers, industry leaders, and the general public.

Four phases will guide the implementation of the activities described in WP6 throughout the project:

- **Phase I - Dissemination and communication strategy (M1-M2)**, this phase involved the definition of the strategy to ensure the achievement of the outcomes and the presentation of the first set of communication and dissemination activities.
- **Phase II - Outreach and awareness activities (M1- M36)**, in which all activities described in this document and the Grant Agreement will be implemented, ensuring the involvement of stakeholders and reaching all target groups, as well as generating synergies and complementarities with all the stakeholders, relevant projects and initiatives.
- **Phase III - Exploitation strategy and training (M12 - M36)**, in which the project outcomes and results will be available, and online training will be created.
- **Phase IV – Post-project sustainability (M36 – five years after the project Completion)**: project legacy and dissemination of key and wider impacts. It is expected that the project's results will be scalable.

As the exploitation phase will start in Month 12, this report will not report actions related to the exploitation phase but will detail the strategy that will be implemented.

2.1 Main objectives of the communication strategy

The project's Dissemination and Communication strategy aims to inform relevant stakeholders and communities about the activities, results, and achievements carried out within the project. Dissemination, communication, and engagement activities follow the strategy developed in Deliverable 6.1, the Dissemination and Communication Plan (Month 2), at the beginning of the project.

The main objectives of this strategy are:

- **Raise Awareness:** Promote the DEPLOYTOUR project to a broad audience to attract and engage stakeholders interested in joining or supporting the pilot activities. This includes participating in and organising events related to tourism and data across local, national, and European levels.
- **Inform and Educate:** Produce and share high-quality, accessible content to explain the concept of data spaces, data sovereignty, and their value for tourism in Europe. Provide relevant stakeholders with clear information on the project's activities, use cases, and achievements.
- **Engage and Mobilise Stakeholders: Encourage tourism stakeholders to adopt and contribute to data-sharing** sovereign practices via the ETDS. Demonstrate how data collaboration can foster innovation, leading to a more competitive, sustainable, and resilient tourism sector.
- **Create synergies:** Promotion of the ecosystem updates, joint communication with other EU projects

The general outcomes of this plan are likely to extend beyond the direct reach of our campaigns. However, the effects on the acquired audience among those targeted can be

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measured through the following KPIs: visitors to the project's website, engagement and reach on LinkedIn publications, events organised and participated in, attendance at online webinars, and contributions to dataspace strategic documents.

The strategy and plan evolve according to the project's activities, needs, and monitoring results.

Project presentations and demonstrations have been done regularly during the past twelve months at key European and international congresses and events.

2.2 Project Communication and Outreach Landscape Analysis

To continuously improve the communication and dissemination strategy, a Strengths, Weaknesses, Opportunities, and Challenges (SWOC) Analysis has been conducted. This analysis aims to inform and enhance actions for the remainder of the project.

Strengths

- **Strong partner engagement:** DEPLOYTOUR benefits from an actively involved and diverse consortium of 43 partners across 13 countries, many of whom regularly promote the project on their social media channels, newsletters and at national and international events.
- **Growing LinkedIn presence:** The LinkedIn page, inherited from the DATES preparatory action, has built a solid audience with over 2,000 followers and consistent engagement from DEPLOYTOUR partners.
- **Effective event representation:** DEPLOYTOUR has been featured in more than 80 tourism and data-related events in the first 9 months of the project, enhancing visibility across sectors.
- **Solid brand identity:** A unified visual identity and communication templates facilitate consistent and professional representation of the project.
- **Cross-sectoral part of the consortium: European Data Space for tourism, thanks to this, it is also well known in the countries, sectors and domains** which are not related to tourism. This helps create Data exchange at the European level in tourism and many other industries, such as mobility, manufacturing, energy, and health.

Weaknesses

- **Prioritisation:** The priority of a deployment project is naturally the implementation of use cases, which consumes efforts from partners, and may be subject to external factors (seasonality, holiday...) and the communication is directly linked to the time they can allocate to this secondary task.
- **Under-engagement from SMEs:** Communication materials and messages are not yet fully tailored to small and medium-sized enterprises (SMEs) in tourism, a key audience for data space adoption.
- **Fragmented tracking:** Given the high volume of outreach, it remains challenging to comprehensively track all dissemination efforts and event participation across the consortium.
- **Complexity of some internal process to validate the content:** The consortium is composed of a wide variety of stakeholders, including large groups, that might centralise their communication. Obtaining content or getting them to post on their page can be challenging tasks.

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Opportunities

- **Leverage partners’ networks:** Many consortium partners have extensive local, national, and European networks that can be mobilised to expand project visibility and reach.
- **Showcase pilot results:** As the five use cases progress, concrete results and demonstrators will offer valuable content to share with stakeholders and build credibility.
- **Reinforce links with other data spaces:** Collaborations with projects like deployEMDS and other Common European Data Spaces, DSSC, and Gaia-X create cross-dissemination opportunities and synergies.
- **Media and press outreach:** Increased media engagement can help reach broader and non-specialist audiences, reinforcing awareness around data sharing and tourism transformation.
- **Active website traffic:** The project website receives regular visits, especially to key sections like “Events” and “Resources,” indicating public interest.

Challenges

- **Audience segmentation:** It remains difficult to precisely assess which stakeholder groups are engaging with each type of content (e.g., SMEs vs. public authorities).
- **SME engagement:** Many SMEs lack the digital skills and capacity to feel concerned about participating in data spaces, though they might find the topic interesting.
- **Monitoring consistency:** Ensuring that all partners regularly update the dissemination tracking tool is a logistical and operational challenge, in particular when individual profiles are concerned and not only corporate pages (on social media).
- **Long-term engagement:** Sustaining interest and interaction throughout the project lifecycle requires varied formats and messaging tailored to different phases and audiences.

2.3. Content strategy

The content strategy is structured around the project’s key messages and is aligned with the project’s maturity.

The content produced aligns with the outreach and exploitation strategy, designed to raise awareness, inform and educate stakeholders, foster engagement, and create synergies.

The content is designed to introduce the project, engage audiences through ongoing activities, promote use case pilots, foster synergies with related data space initiatives, feature consortium partners, highlight event participation, and curate ecosystem updates to keep stakeholders informed. Each piece is customised for optimal delivery, whether through the website, social media, flyers, presentations, articles, videos, or other formats, and adapted to resonate with specific target audiences.

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The table below describes the different types of content that are produced throughout the project:

Content Type	Purpose	Format Examples	Frequency	Targets
Project Overview Content	Introduce DEPLOYTOUR, its objectives, and use cases.	Website, flyers, presentation decks, Posts on social media, Video, Newsletter, Webinar	At project launch, it is updated regularly	All targets
DEPLOYTOUR Activities	Engage the audience with the available activities and opportunities offered by the project.	Posts on social media, Website, Webinar, Newsletter, Training Programme, Posts by partners, Articles by partners, articles in local media	Depend on the activities to promote	Specific targets for each activity
DEPLOYTOUR results and Pilot Stories	Showcase the real-world impact of the pilots.	Posts on social media, articles on local media by the partners, podcast interviews, webinars, case studies, blog posts, Publication in Peer reviews, Scientific press and creation of White paper	Depends on the results that can be promoted	All targets are concerned, but with specific angles tailored to their individual interests. However, this particular content type is the most relevant for the General public and the media.
Cross-Sector Synergies	Disseminate knowledge and foster dialogue on data spaces and tourism, and create synergies with other initiatives, in collaboration with WP5.	Live webinars, YouTube recordings, registration forms, and promotion on social media	At least six over the project duration	Data Space Community and EU decision makers, local and public authorities
Partner Spotlights	Highlight partner contributions and expertise	LinkedIn posts, interviews, short videos	One video per partner promoted on LinkedIn	Business and operational stakeholders in

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				the field of Tourism
Events Coverage	Participation in data and tourism events to increase visibility, outreach and build synergies at local, national, and EU events	Event section of the website, LinkedIn posts, and communication by the partners on their website and social media	For each attended or hosted event	Business and operational stakeholders in the field of Tourism and data
Promotion of content produced by the data space ecosystem	Highlight key news and activities of the European Data Space ecosystem (DSSC, IDSA, BDVA, GAIA-X, SIMPL...)	Post on social media	For each relevant content	Technology stakeholders

Table 1: Content Strategy

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2.4 Communication, dissemination and exploitation plan

To provide a comprehensive overview of the project’s ongoing activities and facilitate proactive planning for WP6, the following Gantt chart is continuously updated throughout the project. It incorporates new initiatives, such as webinars and partner events, developed in collaboration with WP5.

Figure 1: WP6 Gantt Chart

The Gantt chart aligns with the Communication, Dissemination, and Exploitation (C&D&E) Plan, offering a high-level visual overview of WP6 activities, including key tasks and their scheduled timelines. While the Gantt chart provides a broad perspective of the project’s timeline, the C&D&E Plan serves as a detailed, centralised planning tool, implemented through a shared Excel file.

The C&D&E plan compiles all actions undertaken and planned to implement the various tasks of WP6, ensuring anticipation, transparency, and alignment with project goals (which include raising awareness, informing and educating, engaging identified stakeholders, and creating synergies). The plan is broken down per task.

The plan organises activities based on the tasks outlined in the grant agreement (6.1, 6.2, and 6.3), with detailed descriptions for each:

- **Task 6.1: Dissemination and Communication Strategy.** This task centres on Deliverable 6.1, which defines the strategy for outreach and engagement.
- **Task 6.2: Outreach and awareness strategy.** This task encompasses a wide range of activities, including:
 - Development of the project’s visual identity, template documents, and communication guidelines.
 - Website management: Design, maintenance, and regular updates for the "Resources" section.

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- Social media management: Content calendar, post design, quality control, and publishing on LinkedIn and X, along with KPI monitoring.
- Implementation of new tools for social media, newsletters, and webinars.
- Newsletter releases (internal and external).
- Webinar programming: Internal sessions and external webinars (in collaboration with WP5).
- In-person events: Kick-off meetings, partner gatherings, high-level events, and the final event.
- Participation in key annual data and tourism events.
- Article planning for the website.
- Creation and update of a presentation deck for DEPLOYTOUR.
- Press release scheduling.
- Video production: Project presentation, webinar replays (hosted on YouTube and embedded on the website) and any other relevant videos that should be created.
- Design and production of collaterals: Roll-ups, flyers, and stationery.
- Continuous KPI monitoring throughout the project.
- Creation of the Deliverable 6.2
- **Task 6.3: Exploitation and Training strategy.** This task includes:
 - Development of the exploitation strategy.
 - Creation of an online training program.

Note: WP6 is currently defining the specific content for this task, which begins in Month 12. Updates will reflect partner contributions, including scientific outputs (white papers, publications, and handbooks), as well as training modules. Drafting for these activities is underway and will be added to the plan.

The plan is aligned with the project timeline and accessible to all partners. It is regularly updated to reflect project evolution and emerging needs.

Completed tasks are highlighted in green for easy tracking.

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The table below represents the Communication, Dissemination and Exploitation plan:

Task	Description	Partners	Objectives	Deadline	Start	End	Recurrence	Status
6.1: Dissemination and communication strategy	Deliverable 6.1_Dissemination and communication strategy	DISSET, EONA-X, ANYSOL	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Redaction of the deliverable - Implementation of the Monitoring Tool - Definition of the communication and dissemination strategy 	M2 - November 2024	M1	M2		Approved
6.2: Outreach and awareness activities	Creation of the visual identity, project template documents and communication guidelines	DISSET, EONA-X, ANYSOL	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Establish a cohesive brand identity for the project: developing uniform and essential materials for partners - Provide guidelines and tools to meet KPIs and effectively disseminate outcomes while - Be in line with communication obligations as beneficiaries of European project funding 	M1 - October 2024	M1	M1		Done
	Website	DISSET, EONA-X, ANYSOL	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Design of the website and elaboration of its content - Intranet development and release - Pop-up release to support WP5 Mapping Campaign - Maintenance and regular updates of the "Resources" section 	Milestone 11: Launch of the website in Month 6	M1	M36	Sections "Events" and "Resources" are updated regularly	
	Social media	All Partners	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Content Calendar (example of posts: promote DEPLOYTOUR activities, presence at events, engage audience with project's activities, share updates from the ecosystem) - Post Design 	/	M1	M36	On average, three posts per week	

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Task	Description	Partners	Objectives	Deadline	Start	End	Recurrence	Status
			<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Quality check - Posts on LinkedIn and X - Answering comments - Monitoring the posts 					
	Tools	DISSET, EONA-X	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Social Media Management Tool - Newsletter Tool - External Webinar Tool - Canva tool 		M1	M36	New tools may be added upon request and need	
	Newsletter	EONA-X, DISSET, ANYSOL	External #1 - 19.12.24 Internal #1 - 18.12.24	M3				Published
		EONA-X, DISSET, ANYSOL	External #2 - 25.03.25 Internal #2 - 04.04.25	M6				Published
		EONA-X, DISSET, ANYSOL	External #3 - 16.04.25	M6				Published
		EONA-X, DISSET, ANYSOL	External #4 - 05.06.25 Internal #3 - 23.06.25	M9				Published
		EONA-X, DISSET, ANYSOL	External #5 - Sept 2025 Internal #4 - Sept 2025	M12				In progress
		EONA-X, DISSET, ANYSOL	External #6 - Dec 2025 Internal #5 - Dec 2025	M15				
		EONA-X, DISSET, ANYSOL	External #7 - March 2026 Internal #6 - March 2026	M18				
		EONA-X, DISSET, ANYSOL	External #8- Juin 2026 Internal #7 - June 2026	M21				
		EONA-X, DISSET, ANYSOL	External #9 - Sept 2026 Internal #8 - Sept 2026	M24				

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Task	Description	Partners	Objectives	Deadline	Start	End	Recurrence	Status
		EONA-X, DISSET, ANYSOL	External #10 - Dec 2026 Internal #9 - Dec 2026	M27				
		EONA-X, DISSET, ANYSOL	External #11 - March 2027 Internal #10 - March 2027	M30				
		EONA-X, DISSET, ANYSOL	External #12 - June 2027 Internal #111 - June 2027	M33				
		EONA-X, DISSET, ANYSOL	External #13 - sept 2027 Internal #12 - Sept 2027	M36				
Internal Webinar		ANYSOL	- DSSC presentation to DEPLOYTOUR partners' Webinar - 20/01/25	M4				KPI: 1/6
		ANYSOL, EONA-X, NTT, AMADEUS	- Data Space concepts clarifications 06/02/25	M5				KPI: 2/6
			Topic to be confirmed					
			Topic to be confirmed					
			Topic to be confirmed					
External Webinar		ANYSOL, EONA, EUROPEANA	DEPLOYTOUR Beyond Borders: Tourism, Data & Cultural Heritage - 07/05/25	M8				Done, replay available
		ANYSOL, EONA	DEPLOYTOUR Beyond Borders: Tourism, Data & DS4SSCC (smart cities) - 06/06/25	M9				Done, replay available
		ANYSOL, EONA	DEPLOYTOUR Beyond Borders: Tourism, Data & Mobility - 04/09/25	M12				Communication campaign launched

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Task	Description	Partners	Objectives	Deadline	Start	End	Recurrence	Status
		ANYSOL, EONA, ARCTUR	DEPLOYTOUR Beyond Borders: Tourism, Data & Language - Nov 2025	M14				
		IIC, EONA-X	DEPLOYTOUR and cross-sectoral cooperation (MOBI-X, STICS) OCT 2025	M13				
DEPLOYTOUR in-person Events		All Partners	Kick-off Meeting	M1				
		All Partners	Partner Meeting	M8				
		All Partners	High Level Event 2025	M14				
		All Partners	Partner Meeting	M14				
		All Partners	High Level Event 2026					
		All Partners	Partner Meeting					
		All Partners	High Level Event 2027					
		All Partners	Final Event					

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Task	Description	Partners	Objectives	Deadline	Start	End	Recurrence	Status
	Key Events Related to Data and Tourism	All Partners	Participating in almost all events related to tourism and data, such as: - European Big Data Value Forum (EBDVF) - Tourism Innovation Summit (TIS) - European Tourism Forum - FITUR - BTM Italia - ITB Berlin - Data Spaces Symposium - GAIA-X Summit - European Tourism Day - Destinations Exchange Europe - Viva Technology - Destinations Summit - Smart City Expo		M1	M36	Every year	
	Website article	EONA-X	#1 Kick Off Meeting	M2				Published on the website
		EONA-X	#2 European Data Strategy	M6				Published on the website
			To be decided					
			To be decided					
			To be decided					
	General Presentation of DEPLOYTOUR (PPT)	EONA-X, DISSET, ANYSOL	PowerPoint about DEPLOYTOUR		M1	M36	Updated throughout the project	
	Press Release	DISSET	Kick-Off Meeting	M1				
			Following the High-Level Event #1	M14				

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Task	Description	Partners	Objectives	Deadline	Start	End	Recurrence	Status
			Following the High Level Event #2					
			Key deliverable releases					
			Following the High Level Event #3					
			Final Event					
Video of the project		EONA-X, DISSET, ANYSOL	Common European Data Space context and DEPLOYTOUR		M6	M7		Presentation available on YouTube and embedded on the website
		EONA-X, DISSET, ANYSOL	Webinars and stakeholder forums are replayed on YouTube and embedded on the website.		M7	M36	Replays are released after each webinar and stakeholder forum	Replays available: - DEPLOYTOUR Beyond Borders: Tourism, Data & Cultural Heritage_ Webinar #1 – M7 - DEPLOYTOUR Beyond Borders: Tourism, Data & DS4SSCC (smart cities) Webinar #2 – M8 - Stakeholder Forum #1 – M8
		EONA-X, DISSET, ANYSOL	New videos may be released to illustrate the pilots.		M12	M36		
Collaterals		EONA-X, DISSET, ANYSOL	- Roll up - Stationary - Flyers	M6				Materials available on the Repository,

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Task	Description	Partners	Objectives	Deadline	Start	End	Recurrence	Status
	KPI Monitoring	All Partners	A shared Excel document that compiles all communication and dissemination efforts to follow each partner's actions in communicating and disseminating the project.		M1	M36	Updated every month by the partners	
	Deliverable 6.2	WP6 Partners	Dissemination, communication and exploitation report	M12	M9	M12		In progress
6.3: Exploitation strategy and training	Exploitation strategy	UIB, EONA-X, ANYSOL, WP leaders	Identification and cataloguing of the project's Key Exploitable Results (KERs)	M24	M12	M24		
		UIB, ANYSOL, UNL, DISSET	Scientific Exploitation (publications, conference, handbook)	M36	M12	M36		Identification of partners that can be involved in this task
	External Training	UIB, ANYSOL, EONA, DISSET, ITI	External training Tourism Data Spaces	M36	M12	M36		Identification of partners that can be involved in this task

Table 2: Communication, Dissemination and Exploitation Plan

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2.5 Target Audiences, Key Messages & Communication Channels overview

As outlined in the Deliverable 6.1 *Dissemination and Communication Plan*, DEPLOYTOUR actively involves different stakeholder groups by utilising various channels to communicate and disseminate DEPLOYTOUR project content.

As a summary, DEPLOYTOUR engages a diverse range of stakeholders. The project's target audiences include:

- EU decision-makers and public authorities (such as the European Commission's DG MOVE, DG CONNECT, HaDEA, national ministries, and agencies), who play a pivotal role in shaping policies and frameworks for data spaces. By emphasising the roadmap, technical infrastructure, and governance mechanisms aligned with the European Data Spaces Technical Framework, DEPLOYTOUR highlights how the ETDS enhances data sovereignty, security, and cross-border collaboration, ultimately boosting the competitiveness and sustainability of the tourism sector.
- Business and operational stakeholders, including SMEs, large companies, data providers, and users, are central to DEPLOYTOUR's mission. The project demonstrates how the ETDS provides secure, controlled access to high-quality tourism data, enabling innovative services, process optimisation, and real-world pilot implementations. By showcasing best practices, interoperability, and scalability, DEPLOYTOUR encourages stakeholders to adopt data-sharing practices that drive efficiency, innovation, and sector-wide growth.
- Functional and technology stakeholders, such as consulting firms, tech providers, and data space communities (IDSA, GAIA-X, DSSC, FIWARE), are engaged through the project's focus on interoperability, technical infrastructure, and alignment with European standards. DEPLOYTOUR offers these stakeholders opportunities to stay informed about progress.
- The general public and media are targeted to raise awareness of DEPLOYTOUR's positive impact on tourism experiences. The project communicates how the ETDS enables secure, privacy-conscious data sharing, fostering sustainable and smart tourism solutions through real-life use cases and collaborative ecosystems.

The detailed tab explaining the different target groups, messages and channels associated is available in annex 1.

DEPLOYTOUR employs a multi-channel approach to ensure broad and effective outreach. The project website serves as the central hub for information, hosting events, workshops, and key documents. It facilitates collaboration and engagement with both partners and the wider community.

Social media platforms, particularly LinkedIn, are leveraged to extend reach and engagement. LinkedIn, with its established professional network (including 1,324 followers inherited from the DATES project), is used to share updates, promote events, and foster community interaction. X and YouTube complement this strategy by disseminating visual and multilingual content, showcasing project developments, and highlighting progress in use cases.

To maintain consistent and targeted communication, DEPLOYTOUR produces two types of newsletters:

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- An internal newsletter keeps consortium partners informed about milestones, meetings, and achievements.
- An external newsletter, distributed quarterly via the website and LinkedIn, engages a broader audience with updates on activities, workshops, publications, and training materials.

Additional channels include website articles for regular updates, press releases for major milestones, and physical materials such as roller-ups, which are used at events to reinforce brand visibility and communicate key project messages. This integrated approach ensures that DEPLOYTOUR's key messages reach the right audiences through the most effective channels, driving awareness, engagement, and adoption of the ETDS.

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3. Activities carried out

3.1 Dissemination and communication internal procedures

To ensure coherent and effective communication and dissemination across the DEPLOYTOUR consortium, several internal mechanisms have been established:

- **Guidelines and Methodologies**

A dedicated **Communication Guidelines document** was developed at the beginning of the project, ensuring all partners adhere to the required standards when communicating about the project, in line with our communication obligation as European project beneficiaries. This internal resource provides:

- Visual identity rules (logo usage, fonts, colours, etc.)
- Template documents
- Social media procedures
- Guidelines on how to monitor and complete an Excel document that compiles all communication and dissemination efforts of the partners

- **Coordination Meetings**

Every month, AnySolution, DISSET, and EONA-X meet to coordinate the WP6 actions and plan the next steps.

- **Monthly WP6 Meetings**

A monthly meeting is held with all partners involved in WP6. These meetings serve to:

- Review of the past actions
- Present the upcoming activities
- And share how the partners can be involved

Meeting minutes and presentations are stored in the repository.

- **Internal Newsletter**

A quarterly internal newsletter is sent within the consortium to share:

- Key project updates and milestones
- Upcoming activities and events
- Requests for input and contributions from partners

- **Tools and Platforms**

To support these activities, several digital tools are used:

- **Canva**: For the mini workshops of WP3, to help design the ETDS rolebook.
- **Zoom**: To host the webinars and Stakeholder Forum of DEPLOYTOUR
- **SharePoint & Internal Repository**: For storing and sharing materials and templates

3.2 Content released via the different communication channels

DEPLOYTOUR benefits from different channels to maximise visibility, promote project activities, and ensure engagement with both internal and external stakeholders.

3.2.1 Website

The DEPLOYTOUR website¹ serves as the central pillar of visibility, around which all dissemination activities of the project revolve. The website was initially launched as a simple

¹ <https://deploytour.eu/>

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landing page just in time for the Palma KOM in early November 2024 and has since been gradually expanding its sections.

Figure 2: DEPLOYTOUR Home Page

The visual design of the website was meticulously crafted to ensure consistency with the core elements of DEPLOYTOUR’s corporate identity. It reflects an image of modernity and European cohesion, connecting data and tourism in a way that is easily replicable across future physical or digital outputs.

As a milestone, the website was due in Month 6. The main pages (Home, The Project, Use Case Pilots, Contact) were launched in December 2024, with the Events and Resources pages becoming available in February 2025.

The **Home page** is modern and dynamic, featuring clean sections and clear highlights that offer key information about the essence of DEPLOYTOUR. The homepage visual was intentionally chosen, combining elements of heritage and the sea, without being tied to a specific identifiable location.

The **“The Project”** section provides detailed information on the initiative's purpose and vision, complemented by audiovisual elements and an original map with a distinctive aesthetic that highlights the different consortium members.

The **Use Case Pilots** section has also evolved over the months, featuring a cohesive and easily recognisable visual identity based on the graphic design created for the maps. Specific efforts were made to identify the participating partners for each pilot clearly.

The **Events** section is one of the most significant parts of the website, as it visually showcases basic information about both upcoming and past activities. Instead of opting for a standard calendar format with limited customisation, a richer and more versatile display was chosen. It allows users to view the events either as a list or in the more traditional monthly agenda format. It is regularly updated to keep the DEPLOYTOUR community informed about the project's presence at local, national, European, and internal events.

The **Resources** section has been continuously expanding, incorporating not only the current needs of the project but also anticipating future requirements. It already functions as a structured repository, featuring released newsletters, webinar replays, Stakeholder Forums replays, blog articles, and public deliverables.

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Finally, the website includes a **dedicated area for project partners**, which hosts the entire working document repository. This space is organised by work groups and provides access to all templates, meetings, transcripts, and both public and private documents, facilitating smooth collaboration among all members of the DEPLOYTOUR consortium.

3.2.2 Social Media

DEPLOYTOUR's social media strategy prioritises LinkedIn as the primary platform, given its relevance to the project's target audiences. While the project maintains a presence on X² and YouTube, engagement on X has been lower, leading to a strategic shift: fewer posts are shared on X, while LinkedIn and YouTube remain the focus for high-impact content dissemination.

The DEPLOYTOUR LinkedIn account³ has been built on the existing community established by the preparatory actions, DATES. This strategic decision enables DEPLOYTOUR to leverage DATES' established network.

DEPLOYTOUR social media is used to:

- **Present the project, invite stakeholders to DEPLOYTOUR's events, promote its activities and present partners of the consortium:**

Project presentation

DEPLOYTOUR events

Promotion of DEPLOYTOUR activities

Partner Presentation

Figure 3: Example of LinkedIn Posts to present DEPLOYTOUR

² <https://x.com/DEPLOYTOUR>

³ <https://www.linkedin.com/company/deploytour/>

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• Promote DEPLOYTOUR presence at tourism and data events

DEPLOYTOUR presence at Tourism and Data Events

Figure 4: Example of LinkedIn Posts to promote DEPLOYTOUR presence at events

• Share educational content to explain the various concepts of the project, such as data spaces and the Common European Data Space, share news from the ecosystem and promote partners' events where DEPLOYTOUR is presented.

Pedagogical content

Ecosystem News

DEPLOYTOUR presented at Partners' events

Figure 5: Example of other LinkedIn posts

On average, three posts per week are published on the DEPLOYTOUR LinkedIn page, with regular posts also shared by consortium partners.

The following graph illustrates the proportion of content topics on the DEPLOYTOUR LinkedIn page, providing an overview of the segmentation by theme. Posts promoting DEPLOYTOUR activities account for half of all publications, followed by content highlighting partner participation in local, national, European, and international events focused on tourism and data.

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Figure 6: proportion of content topics on the DEPLOYTOUR LinkedIn page

Upon examining the main post category, 'DEPLOYTOUR activities,' nine subtopics can be identified.

The content aimed at engaging participants in DEPLOYTOUR webinars and stakeholder forums represents the main posts of this category.

Currently, posts introducing consortium partners represent a significant portion of this category, as well as promotion of key events such as the kick-off meeting in Mallorca and the partner meeting in Paris.

It is worth noting that the distribution of these posts will evolve as the project progresses. For instance, partner introductions will soon conclude, and the focus will transition toward pilot implementations and their outcomes.

Figure 7: DEPLOYTOUR LinkedIn posts sub-topics

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To encourage stakeholders to participate in the project’s activities and events planned by the DEPLOYTOUR consortium, EONA-X has created some communication campaigns consisting of the creation of specific communication materials (such as visuals for social media and templates of posts). This particular communication material is proposed and shared with the partners. Partners can thus translate and disseminate the information at the local level. So far, two communication campaigns have been set up:

- Stakeholder Forum: 3 post templates
- Webinar DEPLOYTOUR Beyond Borders: Tourism, Data & Mobility: 3 post templates, LinkedIn Event, Article on EU Tourism Platform.

These two campaigns enabled the attraction of a wide range of stakeholders and were more effective than simply communicating on DEPLOYTOUR pages.

Additionally, partner contributions further expand the project’s reach and engagement across relevant communities. The partners share DEPLOYTOUR posts on their LinkedIn Company pages and sometimes with their personal profiles to increase the posts' visibility.

Below are examples of posts published by the consortium:

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Kick Off Meeting in Mallorca – 4th/5th November 2024

Figure 8: Pleiades sharing their participation in DEPLOYTOUR and the kick-off meeting

Figure 9: Polimi sharing their participation in DEPLOYTOUR and the kick-off meeting

Figure 10: The Data Appeal Company sharing their participation in DEPLOYTOUR and the kick-off meeting

Figure 11: Plexus Tech is sharing their participation in DEPLOYTOUR and the kick-off meeting

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Event participation	
<p>AnySolution 2,441 followers 8mo • Edited •</p> <p>Today, the 23rd #EuropeanTourismForum took place in Budapest, Hungary. AnySolution is proud to have been invited by the Hungarian presidency of the EU and the European Commission as coordinator of major EU strategic projects in #tourism, such as DEPLOYTOUR-Deployment European Tourism Data Space and D3HUB - EU Competence Centre to support data management in tourism destinations</p> <p>Hungarian Tourism Agency Dolores Ordoñez Misa Labarile, PhD European Commission Andrés Martínez Vidal iUrban Olivier Ponti ForwardKeys Joshua Ryan-Saha TravelTECH Edoardo Colombo Oliver Csendes João Miguel Vaz Alexandre</p> <p>42 likes • 5 reposts</p>	<p>AnySolution 2,441 followers 8mo • Edited •</p> <p>AnySolution Takes Part in the First Spanish Data Spaces Summit by Gaia-X Our General Director, Dolores Ordoñez, who also serves as Vice-President of Gaia-X Hub España, actively participated in this prestigious event</p> <p>She presented DEPLOYTOUR-Deployment European Tourism Data Space during the Tourism Strategy Panel, where she also moderated an engaging discussion alongside David Collazos SEGITTUR-Sociedad Mercantil Estatal para la Gestión de la Innovación y las Tecnologías Turísticas and Paco Álvarez Caballero Ávoris. Additionally, Dolores showcased innovative use cases for tourism data spaces, highlighting their transformative potential for the industry</p> <p>Enrique Martínez Marín Carlos Romero Dexeus Francisca Rubio Daniel Sáez Domingo Juan Ortells EONA-X Jonathan Huffstutler Carlos Cendra Cruz Mabrian Technologies Official Daniel Caro Turismo Andaluz Ruth del Campo</p> <p>39 likes • 2 comments • 3 reposts</p>
<p>Tourism 4.0 2,768 followers 4mo • Edited •</p> <p>Ecoforum is in full swing in Herceg Novi, Montenegro!</p> <p>Urska Starc Peceny (Arctur / Tourism 4.0) and Miloš Kovačević from the Tourism Organisation of Herceg Novi held a presentation on how destination resilience, ESG in business, and data-driven strategies are shaping the future of tourism.</p> <p>Their presentation was then followed by panel discussion on ESG implementation—moderated by Urska Starc Peceny and featuring:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ◆ Damien Plant (Sustain Develop) ◆ Mat Roberts (Kerry Roberts A) ◆ Prof. Dr. Ivo Županović ◆ Veljko Milošević ◆ Zoran Daljević (Atlantic Group) <p>Key takeaways? ESG isn't just a buzzword—it's a roadmap to a more resilient and responsible tourism industry.</p> <p>That is also what DEPLOYTOUR-Deployment European Tourism Data Space project, which was also presented at the forum, is all about - community building and ecosystem development and synergies with other data spaces, projects, and initiatives.</p> <p>Read more: https://lnkd.in/dxqqvizn</p> <p>#Ecoforum2025 #ESG #SmartTourism #ResilientDestinations #Montenegro #TourismStrategy #DataForGood D3HUB - EU Competence Centre to support data management in tourism destinations</p> <p>11 likes • 2 reposts</p>	<p>Eduardo Martin Crespo • 1st Project Manager @ NTT DATA Data Spaces, Interoperability & Semantics for ... 6mo •</p> <p>¡Desde NTT DATA Europe & Latam estaremos en FITUR 2025!</p> <p>Este año, DEPLOYTOUR-Deployment European Tourism Data Space será presentado por su coordinadora, AnySolution Dolores Ordoñez, PhD, junto a los socios AdQuiver y Turismo Andaluz en FITUR, la Feria Internacional de Turismo en Madrid.</p> <p>📅 Miércoles, 22 de enero, a las 13:15 CET 📍 Sesión: Resiliencia y competitividad de destinos turísticos maduros en el Espacio Europeo de Datos de Turismo 🔊 Descubre cómo la tecnología está ayudando a gestionar destinos y a mejorar la experiencia turística.</p> <p>Como miembros del consorcio del proyecto, desempeñamos un papel clave como líderes técnicos en el desarrollo del Espacio Europeo de Datos de Turismo.</p> <p>#dataspaces #datasharing #tourismdataspace #EUTourism #FITUR #FITURTECHY #TECHYDESTINO #deploytour</p> <p>European Health and Digital Executive Agency (HaDEA) European Commission Agnieszka Bajno Árpád Welker</p> <p>Show translation</p> <p>DEPLOYTOUR Presentation 22-26 January 2025 FITUR International Tourism Trade Fair</p> <p>DEPLOYTOUR Co-funded by the European Union www.deploytour.eu Grant Agreement number 101073388</p>

Figure 12: AnySolution presenting DEPLOYTOUR at the European Tourism Forum (12/14 November 2024)

Figure 13: AnySolution presenting DEPLOYTOUR at the First Data Spaces Summit by Gaia-X (03/04 December 2024)

Figure 14: Arctur presenting DEPLOYTOUR at the Ecoforum (10 April 2025)

Figure 15: NTT Data is sharing their participation in FITUR (January 2025), promoting a roundtable about DEPLOYTOUR

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Filippo Renga • 1st
Coordinator of EU & International Activities
4mo •

Data Spaces are a Strategic Asset for the Entire EU and a way for the World to avoid Digital Oligarchy.

The #DataSpaces Symposium is a must attend event. This has been the first we attended as **Osservatori Digital Innovation**, but it has been a really important occasion to discuss with interesting people on interesting thoughts.

Thank you to the organizers: **Ulrich Ahle** (Gaia-X Association for Data and Cloud (AISBL)), **Hahn Thomas** (BDVA - Big Data Value Association), **Yasunori Mochizuki** (FIWARE), and **Reinhold E. Achatz** (International Data Spaces Association (IDSA)).

Thank you to some of the speakers: **Boris Otto**, **Michal Gramatyka**, **Marko Turpeinen**, **Sébastien PICARDAT**, **Bettina Tratz-Ryan**, **Douglas Ramsey**, **Matthijs Punter**, **Edward Curry**, **Lars Nagel**, **Erich Barnstedt**

Concerning data spaces, we are happy to be part of **DEPLOYTOUR-Deployment European Tourism Data Space**. Thanks to the guide of **Dolores Ordoñez**, **AnySolution**, and all the partners.

40 likes • 3 comments

Figure 16 Polimi's participation in the Data Spaces Symposium, mentioning that they are part of DEPLOYTOUR

Content created by the Partners

CITY DINA | CityDNA
6,671 followers
Learn more
8mo • Edited •

[PRESS RELEASE] // DEPLOYTOUR: Five real-world use cases to deploy a Common European Tourism Data Space //

The DEPLOYTOUR consortium, a collaborative effort of 43 partners from 13 European countries, officially kicked off its ambitious project to revolutionise the tourism industry. The launch event, held in Palma de Mallorca, constituted a crucial step forward in the development of a Common European Tourism Data Space. The project is cofunded by the European Commission.

Read the press release: <https://bit.ly/40AdLLL>
#CityDNA #DEPLOYTOUR #dataspaces #datasharing #tourismdataspace
DEPLOYTOUR-Deployment European Tourism Data Space

21 likes • 1 comment • 2 reposts

Figure 18 The City Destinations Alliance is sharing its press release about participation in the DEPLOYTOUR project.

Eeva Helameri • 2nd
Specialist | Project Manager | Project Planner | at Lapland Uni...
4mo •

Today was a significant day! 🌟
Päivi Hänni-Vaara (she/her) presented our pilot "Empowering SMEs in Tourism through a Collaborative TravelTech Data Space and App Marketplace" at the NECSTouR internal members' webinar "Workshop European Tourism Data Space: Everything You Need to Know". This pilot is part of the **DEPLOYTOUR-Deployment European Tourism Data Space** project. The project aims to boost the competitiveness, sustainability, and resilience of the tourism sector by deploying a trusted Common European Tourism Data Space (ETDS). Lapland University of Applied Sciences and Visit Levi are working closely together to implement the pilot.

Data spaces offer tourism companies a unique opportunity to leverage a broader data mass together with other actors. Collaboration in data spaces can lead to better marketing campaigns, more efficient resource utilization, and reaching new customer segments.

We are excited about this opportunity and look forward to what the future holds! 🙌
Thank you for today's opportunity **Daniel Iglesias Gonsálvez** **Cristina Nuñez**
NECSTouR
#DEPLOYTOUR #dataspaces #datasharing #tourismdataspace #EUtourism #VisitLevi #LaplandUAS

25 likes • 1 repost

Figure 17 Lapland University of Applied Sciences participates in the NECSTouR internal members' webinar "Workshop European Tourism Data Space: Everything You Need to Know" to present their pilot

ITI
13,443 followers
8mo •

El consorcio **DEPLOYTOUR-Deployment European Tourism Data Space**, un esfuerzo colaborativo de 43 socios de 13 países europeos, ha iniciado oficialmente su ambicioso proyecto para revolucionar la industria del turismo.

El objetivo del proyecto es abordar el desafío de los datos turísticos fragmentados e inaccesibles mediante la creación de una plataforma común donde se puedan compartir y utilizar eficazmente datos de diversos interesados.

Al aprovechar el poder de los datos, DEPLOYTOUR permitirá experiencias turísticas más personalizadas, sostenibles y eficientes.

Toda la información en nuestra web: <https://lnkd.in/d/WrJAS9>

European Health and Digital Executive Agency (HaDEA) European Commission AnySolution #DEPLOYTOUR #dataspaces #datasharing #tourismdataspace

Show translation

16 likes • 1 comment

Figure 19: ITI is sharing an article they published about DEPLOYTOUR on their website

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Libelium
20,336 followers
3w • Edited •

Data spaces are already becoming a turning point in how we share, govern and use data across Europe.

At Libelium, we are leading this shift, not just as #technology providers but as strategic partners in the creation of shared infrastructures that enable more sustainable, efficient and coordinated decision-making.

In our new article for Positive Technology, we explore:

How #AI, no-code tools and European federation are accelerating digital transformation

Real use cases like DEPLOYTOUR-Deployment European Tourism Data Space, #Geo4Water, SENSE Cityverse and #BeatTheHeat, already making an impact in tourism, climate change, urban resilience and cybersecurity

Libelium's role as an integrator in this new data ecosystem, driving interoperability, governance and sustainability

Read the full article and discover how #DataSpaces are laying the groundwork for new models of collaboration and data-driven management

<https://lnkd.in/d/cc2a7n>

#BehindtheChange
#BeyondtheChallenge

Figure 20: Libelium is promoting one of their articles on data spaces, which mentioned DEPLOYTOUR

Fraunhofer ISST
3,806 followers
1w • Edited •

Neue Podcastfolge «Die Datenräume» - Mehr Datenqualität für besseres Reisen - Wie Daten den Tourismus resilienter und nachhaltiger machen

Sommer ☀️ Sonne ☀️ Urlaub 🏖️ Wenn wir alle unsere Koffer für die nächste Reise packen, erleben wir hautnah, wie wichtig gut verfügbare und qualitativ hochwertige Daten für das Reisen sind. Natürlich gilt das umso mehr für die Unternehmen im Tourismussektor. Sie brauchen Resilienz, intelligente Betriebsabläufe und gute Nachhaltigkeitsstrategien. Und für alle diese Herausforderungen brauchen sie vor allem eines: Zuverlässige Daten.

Warum Tourismusdaten sehr verstreut sind und wie sie besser genutzt werden können, erzählt Maik Mannsfeld in dieser neuen Episode von «Die Datenräume» - dem Podcast des Fraunhofer-Instituts für Software- und Systemtechnik ISST rund um Innovationen aus Daten. Er ist Projektleiter am Fraunhofer ISST für das Projekt DEPLOYTOUR-Deployment European Tourism Data Space, das auf den Aufbau eines europäischen Datenraums im Tourismus abzielt: 43 Partner aus 13 Ländern und 5 Anwendungsfälle. Ziele wie Resilienz, Nachhaltigkeit und intelligente Prozesse. Zusammen mit Forschungseinrichtungen, Unternehmen und Universitäten.

Deploytour ist nicht nur ein Leuchtturmprojekt für den Tourismus, sondern setzt Maßstäbe für Interoperabilität zwischen Datenräumen in ganz Europa.

Jetzt reinhören und erfahren, wie wir in Zukunft besser reisen:

Spotify: <https://lnkd.in/d/3r9bEQN>
Apple Podcasts: <https://lnkd.in/d/5F5EMazd>
Website: <https://lnkd.in/d/e43CVj>

Habt Ihr Ideen, in welchen Bereichen eine bessere gemeinsame Datennutzung den Tourismus besonders stärken könnte? Schreibt sie uns gerne in die Kommentare!

#InnovationsFromData #Datenräume #DataSpaces #Podcast #DEPLOYTOUR #Tourismus

Show translation

Figure 21: Fraunhofer recorded a podcast to explain DEPLOYTOUR and shared the news on their LinkedIn Page about this new episode.

Partner Meeting in Paris – 12th May 2025

EONA-X
2,654 followers
2mo •

We were thrilled to host the DEPLOYTOUR-Deployment European Tourism Data Space partner meeting today at our EONA-X headquarters in Paris! 🇫🇷

This gathering provided a fantastic opportunity to reconnect with consortium members and strengthen our collaboration. 🤝

7 months after our kick-off, today's discussions emphasized the importance of co-constructing inspiring use-cases where stakeholders can share and utilize data to drive innovation in the tourism sector. 🚀

At EONA-X, we firmly believe that providing a cross-sector, interoperable data sharing infrastructure is pivotal to transforming tourism. 🌐

By fostering trust and collaboration among public and private entities in Europe, we can create more personalized, efficient, and sustainable travel. It's always a pleasure to reunite with our partners, exchange ideas, and reinforce our shared vision. 🌟

Already looking forward to our next meeting!

#DEPLOYTOUR #EONAX #DataSharing #Collaboration #EuropeanTourismDataSpace

Figure 22: EONA-X promoting the Partner Meeting in Paris

hiberus
138,328 followers
2mo •

hiberus at the #DEPLOYTOUR Partners' Meeting in Paris!

The DEPLOYTOUR-Deployment European Tourism Data Space consortium recently came together for an inspiring and productive session focused on shaping the future of the Common European Tourism Data Space (ETDS).

Our colleagues Blanca Adiego Calvo, Lucia Berlanga Garcia and M^a Lorena Prieto represented hiberus at the event, participating in collaborative sessions, insightful discussions, and hands-on workshops—all aimed at tackling key challenges and moving forward with the project's five real-world use cases.

We're proud to be a key technological partner in the project, collaborating closely with the expert consortium to shape the European Tourism Data Space. Our contributions span the design, integration, and deployment of core components, including technical architecture adaptation, implementation of data and metadata catalogues, and the deployment of interoperable data connectors. We focus on ensuring semantic interoperability, enriching metadata, and enabling secure data exchange to support innovative, user-centric tourism services across Europe.

DEPLOYTOUR goals:

- Create a framework for seamless, secure data exchange in tourism
- Support SMEs and DMOs in their digital and sustainable transformation
- Demonstrate the value of ETDS through pilot projects across Europe

The momentum, energy, and shared vision of the 43 partners from 13 countries show how powerful collaboration can be in transforming the industry.

A special thanks to EONA-X, partners of the project, who acted as gracious hosts for the meeting in Paris.

At hiberus, we have spent over 20 years helping companies in the leisure and travel sector redesign their operations, transform the user experience, and reinvent their business models, all with the aim of improving customer relationships and increasing operational excellence. Discover how with our expert team https://lnkd.in/d/yX6_HQM

#WeAreDifferent #LasCasasOurrenAqui #dataspaces #datasharing #tourismdataspace

Figure 23: Hiberus sharing their participation in the Partner Meeting in Paris

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Promotion of DEPLOYTOUR activities	
<p>Figure 25: City Destinations Alliance's post to promote the DEPLOYTOUR video and engage their audience</p>	
<p>Figure 27: AnySolution's post to promote and engage their audience in the mapping campaign</p>	

Table 3: Examples of LinkedIn posts published by the consortium

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3.2.3 YouTube and videos

DEPLOYTOUR has launched a dedicated YouTube channel to host a variety of video content, including webinar replays, conference presentations, and an introductory video about the project. This platform offers audiences easy access to valuable resources, enabling them to explore DEPLOYTOUR’s mission, activities, and impact through engaging visual content.

Figure 28: DEPLOYTOUR YouTube Channel

Since the project's inception, six videos have been produced and shared on YouTube channels to maximise reach and engagement. All replays are also available on the website.

A special video was created to present the context surrounding DEPLOYTOUR and the European data strategy, explain the concept of data spaces, and introduce the DEPLOYTOUR project. This video has been promoted on social media, is used to present the project at events and workshops and is available on the website.

Video	Description	Link
DEPLOYTOUR showcased at FITUR	DEPLOYTOUR was presented by its coordinator, Dolores Ordoñez from AnySolution, alongside project partners Daniel Caro from Turismo Andaluz and Jorge Núñez from AdQuiver, as well as Marco Táboas from Fundació Mallorca Turisme. The session was moderated by Francisca Rubio from Gaia-X Hub España at the FITUR event in Spain. - 06/03/2025	https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=Zb0-6iTviOw
DEPLOYTOUR at the Data Spaces Symposium 2025	During the Data Spaces Symposium on March 10-11, 2025, in Warsaw, Peio Oiz from AnySolution took part in a session focused on the global strategy for data spaces and their interoperability. He was joined on stage by Mariano Blaya-Andreu (IDSA), Dimitrios Gkatzoflias (European Commission), Christopher Newman (Acatech), and Kristof Almasy (European Commission).	https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=n3Fb6HysaEo

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DEPLOYTOUR Beyond Borders: Tourism, Data & Cultural Heritage_ Webinar #1	Webinar Replay In this engaging session held on May 7th, 2025, we explored how data spaces are transforming the tourism and cultural heritage sectors. Experts from the DEPLOYTOUR and Cultural Heritage Data Space projects shared insights on using data to foster sustainability, innovation, and cross-sector collaboration.	https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=rzq7HB8ryi0
DEPLOYTOUR: Developing a trusted and secure Common European Data Space for Tourism	Video to introduce and present the project DEPLOYTOUR.	https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=VrG6vq3CCOo
DEPLOYTOUR Beyond Borders: Tourism, Data & DS4SSCC (smart cities)_Webinar #2	Webinar Replay In this session held on June 6th, 2025, we explored how data spaces are transforming tourism and smart cities. Experts from the DEPLOYTOUR and the European Data Space for Smart Communities (DS4SSCC) projects shared insights on using data to foster sustainability, innovation, and cross-sector collaboration.	https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=im_hOedFt4
Stakeholder Forum: DEPLOYTOUR and the Future of Tourism	DEPLOYTOUR Stakeholder Forum #1 replay: Shaping the Future of Tourism Through Data	https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=sKHHz7RFFq6w

Table 4: Videos on the DEPLOYTOUR YouTube channel

Short videos are also created during events, such as the Kick-off Meeting, workshops, and partner meetings. This type of content is well-received on social media, particularly in formats like reels.

3.2.4 External Newsletter

The external newsletter is published quarterly. To date, four newsletters have been sent on **19 December**, **10 March**, **15 April** (the third newsletter was a special edition focusing on promoting the mapping campaign initiative from WP5), and **5 June**, to a mailing list that has steadily grown over time, with a **124% increase** in recipients between the first and the latest edition. Despite the larger audience, both the **open rate** and the **click-through rate** improved in the most recent newsletter.

This external newsletter provides updates on project activities, insights from partners, and invitations to public events or calls for participation. Subscriptions can be made through the website, either at the bottom of the homepage or on the newsletter page, or via a direct link to the subscription form.

Project partners also contribute by forwarding the newsletter through their own networks and institutional channels, further enhancing reach.

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3.2.5 Internal Newsletter

A quarterly internal newsletter is shared by email by the coordinator among consortium members to align on ongoing activities, highlight key milestones and events, and share upcoming activities for engagement and collaboration. So far, three internal newsletters have been shared with the consortium partners.

3.2.6 Press Releases

The first press release was published on 6 November, covering the Kick-off meeting in Palma. Titled ‘DEPLOYTOUR: Five real-world use cases to deploy a Common European Tourism Data Space’, it was structured in a clear and informative manner, offering a comprehensive overview of the project’s launch event. It began with the introduction of the five pilot projects. It continued with a concise summary outlining the overall scope of the initiative, the composition of the consortium, and its alignment with key European strategies in the fields of digitalisation and tourism. The press release was shared on social media and published on various corporate websites, as well as in the local press of Mallorca.

3.2.7 Printed Materials (flyers, roll-ups)

To enhance outreach beyond digital channels, DEPLOYTOUR utilises printed materials, including flyers and roll-ups, during in-person events. These materials offer visually compelling and informative summaries of the project’s goals, use cases, and key achievements, ensuring clear and impactful communication.

For the official launch event in Palma, a full suite of branded materials was developed to strengthen the project’s visual identity and foster a unified presence among consortium members, reinforcing DEPLOYTOUR’s professional image and cohesive messaging.

Roller-up banners: Two vertical display banners were unveiled at the Kick-off Meeting in Palma. One featured the core motivations behind the initiative, while the other highlighted key information about the five pilots. These visual supports were designed for use at physical gatherings to ensure clear and visually appealing project visibility. Additional versions will be created as needed throughout the project’s lifecycle.

Name badges: Specifically designed for on-site participation, these badges incorporate a deep blue tone, visually reinforcing the European affiliation of the project.

Stationery items such as **pens**, **notebooks**, and **presentation folders** were also produced for distribution in Palma. These elements not only provide practical use but also serve to reinforce brand recognition and consistency at all public and internal appearances.

In parallel, custom templates for presentations and official documents were created, all featuring the consortium’s distinctive visual motif as background, ensuring coherence across all formats and communication outputs.

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Figure 30: DEPLOYTOUR Roll Up

Figure 29: DEPLOYTOUR Stationery

Deployment of the European Tourism Data Space

Our Mission
To develop a trusted and secure common European data space for tourism, to provide better access to information, enhancing productivity, sustainability, innovation, and upskilling across the sector.

Our Vision
To deploy a common infrastructure where data from various stakeholders can be shared and utilized effectively to address the long-standing challenge of fragmented and inaccessible tourism-related data.

Our Goals
To strengthen EU digital sovereignty, build an operational federation of data spaces with a common governance, unlock data's potential for innovation, support Tourism's Transition Pathway (digital and environmental), empower SMEs and DMOs, create new business models supporting the EU data economy.

JOIN THE DEPLOYTOUR COMMUNITY
Subscribe to our newsletter to stay updated on all DEPLOYTOUR news and developments!

For more information: www.deploytour.eu
Follow us:

Project Coordinator: Dolores Ordóñez - AnySolution SL dordonez@anyolution.eu | +34 619 712 806

ANY SOLUTION

Grant Agreement number: 101172388

Co-funded by the European Union. Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or the European Health and Digital Executive Agency (EISMEA). Neither the European Union nor EISMEA can be held responsible for them.

Co-funded by the European Union

Developing a trusted and secure Common European Data Space for Tourism

The project

DEPLOYTOUR is a groundbreaking three-year project, co-funded by the European Union and coordinated by AnySolution. Launched in October 2024, it aims to develop a common, trusted, and secure European infrastructure for tourism.

Building upon the groundwork laid by DATES and DSFT, DEPLOYTOUR focuses on developing data infrastructure, governance, and real-world use case pilots while ensuring synergies with other initiatives.

Our objectives

DEPLOYTOUR is a strategic initiative to boost the competitiveness, sustainability, and resilience of the tourism sector. It addresses the challenges of fragmented and inaccessible tourism data by enhancing access to information, supporting Tourism's Transition Pathway, empowering SMEs and DMOs in their digital and green transition, and fostering innovative practices, upskilling, and productivity for a stronger and more sustainable industry.

43 Partners

13 Countries

03 Years

05 Pilots

The Consortium

The consortium, led by AnySolution, unites 43 partners from 13 countries, creating a dynamic and diverse alliance.

Zoom on the Use Case Pilots

The DEPLOYTOUR consortium is implementing five use-case pilots across Europe to show the tangible advantages of the ETDS and address key challenges in tourism:

- 1. Sustainable Tourism Management in Alpine Regions:** Leveraging AI and data analytics to promote eco-friendly tourism practices and reduce environmental impact (Austria-Slovenia).
- 2. Resilience and Competitiveness in Mature Destinations:** Utilizing data insights to enhance the sustainability and competitiveness of popular destinations like the Canary Islands, Andalusia and the Balearic Islands (Spain).
- 3. Supporting the MICE Industry:** Developing a real-time data tool for MICE professionals, offering personalized, AI-driven insights on transportation, leisure, and cultural activities to meet diverse client needs, in regions like Paris (France).
- 4. Leveraging Cultural Heritage for Tourism Diversification:** Using data to revitalize cultural heritage sites and attract a wider range of visitors and build a sustainable destination model as exemplified by Syros Island (Greece).
- 5. Empowering SMEs in Tourism:** Creating a collaborative platform to connect SMEs with innovative TravelTech solutions and data resources, particularly in regions like Lapland (Finland).

Figure 31: DEPLOYTOUR Flyer

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3.2.8 Templates & Toolkits for Partners

To streamline and align partner communication efforts, a suite of templates and communication toolkits has been made available. These include a slide deck, social media template, document template, project presentation video, and logos, all available in the repository.

These tools help ensure consistent messaging and facilitate localised communication campaigns across different contexts and countries.

3.3 Events and Communication Actions Supported by WP6

3.3.1 Events organised

To date, DEPLOYTOUR has organised two in-person events:

- **Kick-off Meeting in Mallorca** at the beginning of the project (November 2024), which gathered 75 participants, including at least one representative from each partner organisation and speakers from IDSA, FIWARE, DSSC, GAIA-X, UN TOURISM, HaDEA, DG Connect and DG Grow.

Figure 32: Picture of the DEPLOYTOUR consortium at the KOM

- **Partner meeting in May 2025 in Paris.** This second in-person event gathered 52 consortium members for the project's second in-person event. This gathering also fostered synergies with other events, such as the EONA-X Summit, which took place the day after, creating opportunities for DEPLOYTOUR partners to participate in an external event and for attendees of this event to connect with the consortium.

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Figure 33: Picture of the DEPLOYTOUR consortium at the Partners Meeting in Paris

Additional in-person events are planned throughout the project to facilitate consortium meetings and gatherings.

Joint Actions with WP5: Visibility and Communication Support:

It is important to note that Deliverable 6.2 focuses on communication, dissemination, and exploitation activities during the first 12 months of the project. Many of these activities align with those planned under WP5 (Synergies, Recommendations, and Liaison Activities), which will continue until Month 36. Activities such as webinar series and stakeholder forums are designed within WP5, while WP6 enhances their visibility through various communication actions (e.g., social media promotion, banners, etc.).

To support WP5, WP6 has implemented a pop-up on the DEPLOYTOUR website, directing visitors to the mapping campaign questionnaire.

Figure 34: Pop-up on the DEPLOYTOUR website to support WP5 activity

WP5 has developed a series of webinars, stakeholder forums, and a comprehensive mapping campaign scheduled to run until the end of the project. These activities will be detailed in the corresponding WP5 deliverable, D.5.1: Strategic roadmap for collaboration, synergy creation, and community building (M36).

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WP6 has supported the communication and dissemination of these activities by creating a specific communication campaign to promote them on social media, through the external newsletter, the EU platform, and via email. Additionally, WP6 has facilitated the WP5 webinar series and stakeholder forums, as well as the mapping campaign, to reach a maximum number of participants.

Example of a LinkedIn post to promote the Mapping campaign	Promotion of a DEPLOYTOUR webinar on the EU Tourism Platform	Promotion of the Stakeholder Forum in the DEPLOYTOUR External Newsletter

Table 5: Example of communication campaigns to support WP5 activities

With the efforts of WP5 and WP6:

- The first webinar, “DEPLOYTOUR Beyond Borders: Tourism, Data & Cultural Heritage”, held on the 7th of May 2025, had 36 participants.
- The second webinar, “DEPLOYTOUR Beyond Borders: Tourism, Data & Smart Communities”, held on the 6th of June 2024, gathered 50 participants.
- The Stakeholder forum, held on the 26th of June, gathered 70 participants.

3.3.2 Events attended

DEPLOYTOUR partners actively participate in local, national, European, and international events to promote the project. From Month 1 to Month 11, partners attended approximately 85 events, with DEPLOYTOUR being presented at several of them.

Key data and tourism-related events, as well as those featuring DEPLOYTOUR, are listed on the project website under the "Events" section.

The table in Annexe 2 summarises the events attended by DEPLOYTOUR partners and is extracted from the Excel *Communication & Dissemination DEPLOYTOUR Monitoring tool* (also called Monitoring Tool).

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Partners regularly update the table with the following event details:

- Month and name of the event
- Format (online or in-person, including city and country)
- Date
- Event website
- Organiser status (whether the partner is hosting/organising the event)
- Participation confirmation

This system ensures comprehensive tracking of consortium activities and promotes partner involvement on social media, encouraging stakeholders and fellow consortium members to connect and engage at these events.

3.3.3 Workshops

Throughout the project, partners are organising workshops to present the project to their network, especially to involve them in the different pilots.

The table below presents the workshops organised so far to present DEPLOYTOUR:

AnySolution	On 26 June 2025, AnySolution organised the first Deploytour pilot workshop in the Balearic Islands at the ParcBit, with support from the University of the Balearic Islands. The session brought together key tourism stakeholders, including the Consell de Mallorca, Ajuntament de Calvià, AETIB, AENA, Ports de Balears, Fundació BIT, IBESTAT and the Regional Government, to explore a data exchange model tailored to the region. The session focused on aligning efforts, identifying opportunities for collaboration, and laying the groundwork for a shared data catalogue with robust governance and data sovereignty.
EONA-X	On 13 February 2025, EONA-X organised a workshop to explain the data space concept in a game-based approach and start involving local stakeholders in the MICE Pilot. This hybrid workshop gathered 27 people from 18 organisations (EONA-X, Amadeus, The Data Appeal Company, City Destinations Alliance, Vi Paris, Val d’Oise Tourisme, Atout France, Hoose Paris Region, Paris Je t’aime, Expo’stat, UNIMEV, European Exhibition Industry Alliance, ICCA, Allianz Partners, Petit Futé, SNCF, Mastercard, APIDAE). The objective of this workshop was to explain data space concepts and map stakeholders’ challenges in the MICE sector.
IIC	Workshop in Prague on DevelopDataExchange. 20 th of May 2025
IIC	Workshop in Bratislava on DevelopDataExchange. 19 th June 2025
LAPLAND UAS	On 22 May 2025, Lapland UAS organised a workshop with the Levi DMO and Levi Region tourism SMEs. DEPLOYTOUR highlighted the concept of a data space and the benefits of data usage and sharing in practical terms to the participants. Afterwards, the potential use cases, based on interviews conducted earlier, were further collaboratively developed to represent the needs of SMEs. The workshop gathered 15 participants from key organisations in Levi.
Tourism Bohinj	From April to July 2025, 6 workshops were organised to present DEPLOYTOUR and pilot 1 to local stakeholders (Tourism Bohinj, Bohinj Municipality, TNP, Tourist Association Bohinj, as well as to map and synchronise local and regional data sources.

Table 6: Workshops organised to present DEPLOYTOUR

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3.4 Publications and dissemination materials

3.4.1 Project blogs

So far, two blog entries have been published on the official website and social media channels:

- November 18, 2024: *Successful Kick-Off of DEPLOYTOUR: Building a Common Tourism Data Space for Europe*
- March 10, 2025: *The European Data Strategy: A Single Market for Data for a Digital Europe*

All blog posts are available in the designated blog section of the DEPLOYTOUR website.⁴

More blogs will be published with the contribution of partners. Concerning use case pilots, some articles are foreseen when they become more defined, ensuring better quality and interest to readers.

1.1.1 Newsletters, articles, blogs and podcasts across partners

DEPLOYTOUR also benefits from external outreach through partners who share the project and its updates via their own channels, such as newsletters, website articles, and company podcasts.

From Month 1 to Month 11, DEPLOYTOUR has been featured **approximately 45 times** thanks to partners' communication and dissemination on their internal channels.

The table in Annex 3 is extracted from the Monitoring Tool, which is updated monthly by the Partners. It **compiles DEPLOYTOUR's appearances across the consortium's internal communication channels**, which records:

- Partner Name
- Promoted activity (general information, kick-off meeting, a specific pilot use case, partner meeting, participation in events). They can also specify the activity if it is not in the drop-down menu of the list of activities
- Another down menu allows to specify the type of media (My organisation Newsletter, Article on my organisation website, Internal communication channels, Interviews, Podcast)
- Name of the article
- Name of the media
- Date of publication
- Link to the content
- Estimated reach, where measurable

During this period, partners have shared DEPLOYTOUR updates through:

- **25 articles on their organisation website** (Amadeus, Arctur, CityDNA, FRAUNHOFER, ITI, Lapland UAS, Libelium, Ministerio del Turismo, Pleiad, Plexus, STICHTING EUROPEANA, AUSTRIA TOURISM, UIB)
- **At least five communications on partners' internal communication channels** (Amadeus, NTT Data Spain, Trenitalia)
- **At least 16 mentions of DEPLOYTOUR in partners' newsletters** (Arctur, CityDNA, EONA-X, Hiberustec, Lapland UAS, Pleiad, STICHTING EUROPEANA)

⁴ <https://deploytour.eu/resources/blog/>

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- **2 podcast features in partner podcasts** (The Data Appeal Company, FRAUNHOFER)

1.1.2 Media exposure at local, national and European levels

Additionally, visibility is amplified through local, national and European media, including newspapers, press releases, articles, blogs and podcasts.

From Month 1 to Month 11, DEPLOYTOUR has been featured approximately **20 times in external media**, thanks to contributions from the project partners.

The table in Annex 4 is extracted from the Monitoring Tool, which partners update every month. It **compiles DEPLOYTOUR’s appearances in local, national, and European media outlets**. Partners can select from the same drop-down menu as described below whether the media is: European newspaper, National newspaper, Local newspaper, National TV, Local TV, Digital media, Radio, Interviews, Podcast, Blog, or White Paper.

External media highlights include:

- **A blog by AnySolution on the Big Data Value Association website**, titled "Creating a Data-Driven Future for Tourism: Building Sustainable, Resilient, and Competitive Destinations"
- **4 articles on European Newspaper, on the EU Tourism Platform**
- **9 articles on local newspapers** (AnySolution, DISSET, ITI, POLIMI)
- **4 articles on DEPLOYTOUR in National newspapers** (EONA-X, AnySolution)
- **Invited to one podcast**, "Data Space podcast" by Startin' Box (AnySolution)
- **Contribution to a whitepaper** on Data Governance for Tourism by the Gaia-X Tourism Ecosystem (AnySolution)
- **2 press releases** sent by DISSET to Spanish local and national media

1.1.3 Online presence across partners' websites

On the official websites of some partners, there is a section dedicated to DEPLOYTOUR that provides important information about the project and contributes to its visibility. Below are some of the links where the project has been featured:

- Section dedicated on ANYSOLUTION website: [Link](#)
- Section dedicated on MINISTERO DEL TURISMO website: [Link](#)
- Section dedicated on NECSTOUR website: [Link](#)
- Section dedicated on City Destinations Alliance website: [Link](#)
- Section dedicated on Arctur websites: [Link 1](#), [Link 2](#)
- Section dedicated on the Fraunhofer website: [Link](#)
- Section dedicated on Industry Innovation Cluster website: [Link](#)
- Section dedicated on TURIZEM BOHINJ website: [Link](#)
- Section dedicated on Europeana Pro website [Link](#)
- Section dedicated on the ITI website [Link](#)
- Section dedicated on Lapland UAS website: [Link](#)

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4. Results and impact metrics

4.1 Monitoring Tool

Each month, partners complete a shared Excel document that compiles all communication and dissemination efforts, tracking each partner's actions throughout the project.

The Excel is structured in different tabs:

- Tab 1.1: External Events partners attend
- Tab 1.2: Internal Events partners organised under DEPLOYTOUR
- Tab 2.1: Social Media Monitoring
- Tab 2.2 Media Exposure

From M1 to M11, the consortium has compiled in the *WP6_Communication & Dissemination DEPLOYTOUR_Monitoring tool*:

- **85 External events**
- **32 Internal events**
- **357 Social media new posts on all social media (not repost)**
- **67 appearances of DEPLOYTOUR in different media**

4.2 KPIs used to measure the impact of communication

The Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) have been revised and adjusted to reflect the project's goals in a more realistic and achievable way, as discussed during the review meeting. Given the consortium's active participation in numerous events and its frequent promotion of DEPLOYTOUR's foreseen outcomes, the growing momentum around data spaces, artificial intelligence, and the need for quality data in tourism, as well as the appointment of the first-ever Tourism Commissioner, some KPIs have already been achieved in the project's first phase.

Moreover, new KPIs have been set to ensure continuous progress. However, the original KPIs remain relevant and provide a strong framework for monitoring the impact of DEPLOYTOUR's communication efforts.

To further enhance tracking of communication, dissemination, and exploitation efforts, new KPIs were established in September 2025, based on results from the previous year. These KPIs will be monitored throughout the project to ensure comprehensive progress assessment. They reflect the project's objectives and what we are aiming for:

- Accumulated number of LinkedIn followers
- Number of videos on YouTube
- Number of blog articles on the website
- Number of events on the website (user interactions with the website -clicks, downloads, video plays, or form submissions- that are tracked independently of standard page views)
- Total (unique) users on the website
- External newsletter distribution numbers
- External newsletter subscribers
- Internal newsletter distribution numbers
- Number of press releases
- Number of scientific publications

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The table below compiles WP6's KPIs.

Both the original and updated KPIs cover the entire period until the end of the project; the "Current status" column reflects KPIs from October 2024 to August 2025, while "Updated KPIs" covers the period until completion (the new objectives that are set up). **KPIs highlighted in grey** are those originally mentioned in the **Grant Agreement**, while **additional KPIs** have been included to ensure **comprehensive tracking** of WP6's diverse activities.

Tools/ Channels	KPIs – Explanation	KPIs – from the Grant Agreement	Updated KPIs (new objectives from September 25)	Current status	Details
Communication tools & Channels	Number of posts in social networks (not repost)	>1000 posts generated	/	~350 posts	~ 200 posts by DEPLOYTOUR ~ 150 LinkedIn posts by Partners
	Accumulated number of followers on LinkedIn	/	> 2600	2130	
	Number of videos on YouTube	/	15	6	
	Number of blog articles on the website	/	12	2	
	Number of events on the website (user interactions with the website -clicks, downloads, video plays, or form submissions- that are tracked independently of standard page views)	/	90 000	38 919	
	Total (unique) users on the website	/	4000	2585	
Events	Number of online webinars	6 for the project members and invites	/	2 internal webinars	- DSSC presentation to DEPLOYTOUR partners. Webinar - 20/01/25 - Data Space concepts clarifications 06/02/25
	Regular webinars addressed to a wider audience (DMOs, decision makers, tourism professionals, journalists, general public...)		/	2 external webinars	With WP5: -DEPLOYTOUR Beyond Borders: Tourism, Data & Cultural Heritage - 07/05/25 -DEPLOYTOUR Beyond Borders: Tourism, Data & DS4SSCC (smart cities) - 06/06/25

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Tools/ Channels	KPIs – Explanation	KPIs – from the Grant Agreement	Updated KPIs (new objectives from September 25)	Current status	Details
	Number of events organised/participated in	>30 - Kick-off event - Final event - 5 in-person events throughout the duration of the project (1 per pilot destination) - Participating in almost all event related to tourism and data	>250 participation + organisation of events (~83 events per year)	85	
Publications	Contributions to dataspace strategic documents in alliance with the associations	at least 1	At least 3	1	BDVA Blog: <i>Creating a Data-Driven Future for Tourism: Building Sustainable, Resilient and Competitive Destinations</i>
	External Newsletter numbers	/	13	4	
	External Newsletter subscribers	/	350	139	
	Internal Newsletter numbers	/	12	3	
	Number of press releases	/	5	1	
	Number of scientific publications	/	>3	0	

Table 7: KPIs Monitoring

The DEPLOYTOUR project’s ability to build on the existing LinkedIn community from DATES has positively impacted follower growth. However, as the audience expands, social media reach and engagement rates do not scale linearly. Algorithms often reduce proportional reach, and a more diverse audience means that specific topics may resonate with certain segments more than others. While follower growth may remain steady, impressions and engagement rates per post may decline proportionally, though the total volume of views, comments, likes, and shares should continue to increase.

To mitigate these algorithmic limitations, strategic sponsorship of key publications, targeting specific audience segments, will help ensure that DEPLOYTOUR meets its KPIs.

As explained, *some KPIs have been revised*:

The KPI for the number of events organized or participated in has been updated to better reflect DEPLOYTOUR’s participation and event organisation. In the first year alone, the project was represented at approximately 90 events by the coordinator and partners, demonstrating the growing momentum around data spaces in tourism. As a result, the new target is now set at over 250 events, roughly 83 per year, rather than the previously planned 30.

The KPI for "Contributions to data space strategic documents in alliance with associations" has also been revised, as the initial target was already achieved in the first phase. The new KPI is now set at a minimum of 3 contributions to such documents.

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It is essential to note that external webinars are organised in collaboration with WP5, thereby fostering synergies with other data space initiatives.

4.3 Social media statistics, website traffic engagement, and newsletters data

4.3.1 Social media statistics

This section provides an overview of DEPLOYTOUR's presence across various social media platforms, along with an analysis of their traffic data—specifically LinkedIn, X, and YouTube.

All social media icons are prominently placed on the DEPLOYTOUR website's homepage, offering visitors direct access to their respective profiles.

4.3.1.1 LinkedIn

LinkedIn stands out as one of the most effective platforms for sharing professional content. By the end of month 11, the LinkedIn page had accumulated **2,133 followers**. Building on the existing community established by the preparatory actions of DATES, the DEPLOYTOUR LinkedIn account gained **828 new followers** from month 1 to month 11.

Regarding LinkedIn KPIs, only new posts created are considered, not **reposts**. On average, posts published on the LinkedIn DEPLOYTOUR page are reposted 5 times.

Since the project's inception, 153 posts have been published on the DEPLOYTOUR LinkedIn page, and 140 new posts have been shared by DEPLOYTOUR partners on their respective LinkedIn pages, with a total of 726 reposts.

Community growth

See how your community has developed over the period.

Figure 35: LinkedIn Community Growth

This graph illustrates the evolution of followers over time, based on post publication. We can observe that posting regularly, even if the quantity of posts is not substantial, helps attract new followers. Consistency is key.

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Figure 36: LinkedIn page highlights – 01 Nov 2024 – 31 August 2025

In total, from M1 to M11, the DEPLOYTOUR LinkedIn page received a total of around **118,220 organic impressions, 4,380 reactions, 100 comments, and 730 reposts.**

So far, no sponsored campaigns have been launched, but they are planned for the upcoming months to promote the Stakeholder Forum and other DEPLOYTOUR activities.

The most effective posts are those promoting partner meetings, such as the kick-off meeting and the partner meeting in Paris. Additionally, posts that focus on project presentations, the promotion of DEPLOYTOUR activities and events, as well as pictures of partners at events promoting DEPLOYTOUR, perform well.

Top 3 posts with the most impressions:

TOP 1	TOP 2	TOP 3
<p>DEPLOYTOUR-Deployment European Tourism Data Space</p> <p>The #DEPLOYTOUR project kicked off yesterday in Mallorca!</p> <p>This first day of this 3-year European project was a fantastic success. During the morning session, we gained a clear understanding of the European Commission's expectations and felt the support from key organizations like UN Tourism, BDVA - Big Data Value Association, Gaia-X Association for Data and Cloud (AISBL), International Data Spaces Association (IDSA), and FIWARE.</p> <p>Our partners also had the chance to connect, network, and lay the groundwork for the months ahead. And this is only day one!</p> <p>Stay tuned to see what we're building and our vision for the European Tourism Data Space. Big things ahead!</p> <p>#dataspaces #datasharing #tourismdataspace #EUTourism</p> <p>AnySolution European Health and Digital Executive Agency (HaDEA) European Commission Dolores Ordoñez Agnieszka Bajno Árpád Welker ParcBIT AETIB - Agència d'Estratègia Turística de les Illes Balears Sebastián González Govern de les Illes Balears Antonio López de Avila Muñoz Alberto Palomo Clara Pezuela Ana García Robles Data Spaces Support Centre</p> <p>136 reactions · 29 reposts</p> <p>5428 impressions 136 reactions 29 reposts Link to the post</p>	<p>DEPLOYTOUR-Deployment European Tourism Data Space</p> <p>#DEPLOYTOUR Partners' Meeting in Paris!</p> <p>Today, the DEPLOYTOUR consortium came together for a productive and inspiring day dedicated to shaping the future of the Common European Tourism Data Space!</p> <p>A day full of collaboration, insightful discussions, and hands-on workshops that helped tackle key challenges and drive forward the deployment of our five real-world use cases.</p> <p>The energy and shared commitment gave us all a boost to keep building a more competitive, resilient, and sustainable tourism sector through innovation and data sharing.</p> <p>Stay tuned to follow the next exciting steps of the project!</p> <p>#dataspaces #datasharing #tourismdataspace #EUTourism</p> <p>European Health and Digital Executive Agency (HaDEA) European Commission AnySolution Agnieszka Bajno Árpád Welker Politecnico di Milano Osservatori Digital Innovation EONA-X Amadeus NTT DATA Europe & Latam Ministero del Turismo TECNALIA Research & Innovation NECSTour City Destinations Alliance CityDNA Aircur ITI GMV Avonit Österreich Werbung / Austria Tourism Europeana Turismo Andaluz Plexus Tech Fraunhofer ESST Ibericus Unparallel Innovation, Lda Pleiades IoT Innovation Cluster Uni Systems The Data Appeal Company Industry Innovation Cluster Tourism Bohinj Green Movement Lapland University of Applied Sciences DISSET Consultores AETIB - Agència d'Estratègia Turística de les Illes Balears Libellum NOVA IMS Information Management School Trenitalia AdQuiver Universitat de les Illes Balears Breda University of Applied Sciences</p> <p>103 reactions · 17 reposts</p> <p>2832 impressions 103 reactions 17 reposts Link to the post</p>	<p>DEPLOYTOUR-Deployment European Tourism Data Space</p> <p>Help us map tourism-related data-sharing initiatives and Tourism Data Spaces!</p> <p>Are you involved in a data-sharing initiative in the tourism sector or a Tourism Data Space? We're building a complete map of initiatives across Europe. Fill out our short form and be part of this collaborative movement!</p> <p>https://swill.to/khQUIZx</p> <p>#DEPLOYTOUR #dataspaces #datasharing #tourismdataspace #EUTourism</p> <p>European Health and Digital Executive Agency (HaDEA) European Commission AnySolution Agnieszka Bajno Árpád Welker Dolores Ordoñez Politecnico di Milano Osservatori Digital Innovation EONA-X Amadeus NTT DATA Europe & Latam Ministero del Turismo TECNALIA Research & Innovation NECSTour City Destinations Alliance CityDNA Aircur ITI GMV Avonit Österreich Werbung / Austria Tourism Europeana Turismo Andaluz Plexus Tech Fraunhofer ESST Ibericus Unparallel Innovation, Lda Pleiades IoT Innovation Cluster Uni Systems The Data Appeal Company Industry Innovation Cluster Tourism Bohinj Green Movement Lapland University of Applied Sciences DISSET Consultores AETIB - Agència d'Estratègia Turística de les Illes Balears Libellum NOVA IMS Information Management School Trenitalia AdQuiver Universitat de les Illes Balears Breda University of Applied Sciences</p> <p>21 reactions · 6 comments</p> <p>1856 impressions 81 reactions 21 reposts Link to the post</p>

Table 8: Top 3 LinkedIn posts with the most impressions

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Distribution of publications

Analyze the distribution of your publications by type and find out which ones generate the most engagement.

Figure 37: LinkedIn Distribution of publications (M1 – M10)

Most of the posts are illustrated with DEPLOYTOUR visuals (photos), which is why they receive the most impressions. However, we can see that videos and carousels also generate a significant amount of engagement, despite there being fewer posts containing these formats. Therefore, we aim to create more content like this.

On average, posts shared by DEPLOYTOUR partners achieve higher impressions than those published on the project’s official LinkedIn page. For instance, while **DEPLOYTOUR’s posts average 780 impressions, partner posts generate 10% more impressions.** This difference can be attributed to several factors:

- Partners often have larger and more established audiences.
- Their internal communication teams are experienced in crafting content tailored to their specific followers, maximising reach and engagement.

This highlights the value of leveraging partners’ networks to amplify DEPLOYTOUR’s visibility and impact.

4.3.1.2 X (Twitter)

The **DEPLOYTOUR X account has published 52 posts**, while **partners have contributed 10 posts**. Engagement on X, including impressions, reactions, and reposts, remains significantly lower compared to LinkedIn, with limited follower growth.

For example, on average, posts on X receive **97 impressions and three reactions**, whereas on LinkedIn, posts receive, on average, 780 impressions and 30 reactions.

Given these metrics, DEPLOYTOUR’s primary audience is on LinkedIn rather than X. Therefore, **we recommend discontinuing activity on X and focusing our efforts on LinkedIn, YouTube and the EU Tourism Platform, where engagement is substantially higher.**

4.3.1.3 YouTube

The number of subscribers on the DEPLOYTOUR YouTube channel⁵ is 20. Six videos have been uploaded to the channel.

⁵ <https://www.youtube.com/channel/UChzZpewzJVOL7ZJ0xC9mo8Q>

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As shown in the image below, **the most-viewed video is the DEPLOYTOUR presentation video, with a total of 223 views**. This is followed by the replay of the second webinar, "DEPLOYTOUR Beyond Borders: Tourism, Data & DS4SSCC (Smart Cities)", which garnered 45 views. The replays of the first webinar, "DEPLOYTOUR Beyond Borders: Tourism, Data & Cultural Heritage," and the Stakeholder Forum also have 45 views.

Your top content in this period

Content	Average view duration	Views
<p>1 DEPLOYTOUR: Developing a trusted and secure Common European Data Space... May 11, 2025</p>	1:45 (47.3%)	223
<p>2 DEPLOYTOUR Beyond Borders: Tourism, Data & DS4SSCC (smart cities) Jun 13, 2025</p>	2:28 (4.8%)	45
<p>3 DEPLOYTOUR Beyond Borders: Tourism, Data & Cultural Heritage_ Webinar #1 May 11, 2025</p>	3:04 (5.5%)	45
<p>4 Stakeholder Forum: DEPLOYTOUR and the Future of Tourism Jun 27, 2025</p>	3:20 (3.9%)	45

Figure 38: YouTube top content

It is important to underline that the number of views is not the only asset of YouTube. YouTube DEPLOYTOUR's videos also contribute to improving the project's SEO ranking. Since the videos are embedded in the "Resources" section of the DEPLOYTOUR website and include subtitles, they enhance search visibility, making it easier for stakeholders to discover the project. Hosting videos on YouTube strengthens both engagement and online accessibility.

4.3.2 Website traffic

During the first nine months, **the DEPLOYTOUR website recorded 2,000 unique users and over 27,000 events, with more than 9,000 page views. The average engagement time per user was 1 minute and 22 seconds**. This figure shows daily visits during the period from November 1 to August 29.

Figure 39: Website traffic overview

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The homepage is by far the most visited section, with over 7,768 page views. It also attracted the highest number of active users (1,961), accounting for more than 76% of total visitors. However, the average engagement time per user on the homepage is 1 minute and 12 seconds.

The Events section ranks second in popularity, with 1,546 page views and a notably high 6.28 pages per active user, indicating strong user interest and interaction. It also stands out with the highest average engagement time: 1 minute and 23 seconds.

The Use Case Pilots and The Project pages follow in third and fourth position, showing significant user engagement. While “Use Case Pilots” had 1,358 views from 655 users, the “Project” page had 1023 views and a slightly higher engagement time of 44 seconds.

The Private Area, intended for consortium members, received 585 page views, with each user viewing an average of 5.16 pages and spending 1 minute and 45 seconds on average — suggesting purposeful, in-depth use by project partners.

		Page Views	Active Users	Page Views per active user	Engagement time
<input type="checkbox"/>	1 /	7.768 (50,22 %)	1.961 (76,45 %)	3,96	1 min y 12 s
<input type="checkbox"/>	2 /events/	1.546 (10 %)	246 (9,59 %)	6,28	1 min y 23 s
<input type="checkbox"/>	3 /use-case-pilots/	1.358 (8,78 %)	655 (25,54 %)	2,07	34 s
<input type="checkbox"/>	4 /private-area/	1.062 (6,87 %)	206 (8,03 %)	5,16	1 min y 45 s
<input type="checkbox"/>	5 /the-project/	1.023 (6,61 %)	628 (24,48 %)	1,63	44 s
<input type="checkbox"/>	6 /use-case-pilot/sustainable-tourism-management-in-alpine-regions/	232 (1,5 %)	130 (5,07 %)	1,78	34 s
<input type="checkbox"/>	7 /resources/blog/	221 (1,43 %)	95 (3,7 %)	2,33	22 s
<input type="checkbox"/>	8 /contact/	202 (1,31 %)	143 (5,58 %)	1,41	17 s
<input type="checkbox"/>	9 /use-case-pilot/resilience-and-competitiveness-in-mature-destinations/	179 (1,16 %)	105 (4,09 %)	1,70	42 s
<input type="checkbox"/>	10 /resources/newsletters/	174 (1,12 %)	80 (3,12 %)	2,18	18 s

Figure 40: Page views, active users and engagement time metrics

The following figure shows web traffic sources. Most of the traffic to the DEPLOYTOUR website has come from **direct access**, accounting for the largest share of new users. This is followed by **organic search**, indicating a solid presence in search engine results. **Referral traffic**—visits from users clicking links on external websites—represents a smaller but still relevant portion. Finally, **organic social media** contributed the least, suggesting that while social channels are active, they currently play a more limited role in attracting new users to the site.

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Figure 41: Web traffic sources

This figure shows the most active users by country.

Figure 42: Most active users per country

4.3.3 Newsletter data

The newsletter subscriber base has steadily grown over the past months. The first newsletter, sent in December, had only 63 subscribers.

Newsletter analytics #1

Figure 43: Newsletter #1 metrics

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However, the most recent edition, delivered in June, reached 141 recipients, representing a **124% increase**. The **current number of subscribers is approaching 170**. Notably, despite this growing audience, the **open rate** has continued to improve, reaching an impressive **57% in the latest newsletter**.

Newsletter analytics #4

Figure 44: Newsletter #4 metrics

4.4 Impact on the project's visibility

This section analyses how communication and dissemination activities have contributed to:

- **Increasing the project's recognition among target audiences.** The sustained growth in followers and the increase in engagement reflect a genuine interest in the project's results, findings and outcomes.
- **Positioning the project as a reference point in its thematic area.** Participation in international, European and national events have positioned the project as a visible and relevant actor within the European ecosystem.
- **Fostering engagement and growth.** Participation in webinars, active social media interactions, a growing subscriber base for the newsletter, increased website traffic, and invitations to contribute at events all demonstrate the development of a dynamic and thriving ecosystem around the project.
- **Generating media interest.** Mentions in data and tourism media and inclusion in papers or relevant conferences further strengthen the project's authority.

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5. Exploitation strategy

The exploitation strategy of DEPLOYTOUR is designed to ensure that the **project results are transformed into tangible, sustainable value for both the tourism sector and the wider European data ecosystem**. The plan is structured around two complementary pillars:

Dissemination of the Key Exploitable Results (KERs)

The development of a training programme that guarantees the effective adoption of these results.

Having an exploitation strategy to disseminate key results is essential for DEPLOYTOUR because it synchronises the project’s diverse scientific, technical, and dissemination efforts—spanning data-space architecture, governance, pilot deployment, and policy outreach—into a single, coherent roadmap. By knitting together the contributions of all academic partners and industry stakeholders, the plan ensures that findings from each work package accelerate the conversion of research outputs into high-impact publications and FAIR datasets.

Ultimately, this holistic coordination enhances the project’s scientific visibility, streamlines resource utilisation, and positions DEPLOYTOUR as the European reference for tourism data innovation and evidence-based policy making.

The second pillar of the strategy is the training programme, which will operate at two complementary levels. Internal training, within the context of WP4, will be directed at project partners and specifically designed to support the pilots, ensuring that all teams involved share a common knowledge base on the technical, organisational and governance aspects of tourism data spaces. External training will target the wider European ecosystem, including SMEs, DMOS, administrations, researchers, technical positions and citizens. The external training courses will be validated at university level, guaranteeing academic quality and recognition. They will incorporate peer-learning methods that allow participants to benefit from both formal teaching and practical experiences shared within the community.

Exploitation is thus conceived as an integrated process combining two interdependent dimensions. Scientific exploitation will maximise the academic and professional visibility of DEPLOYTOUR, with outputs such as peer-reviewed publications, tools published in FAIR repositories, and the development of a reference handbook on European Tourism Data Spaces. Finally, capacity building and training will serve as the transversal enabler, ensuring adoption, replication, and long-term impact.

5.1 Dissemination of the Key Exploitable Results (KERs)

The exploitation methodology follows a progressive and user-oriented logic. It begins with the early identification and cataloguing of KERs, assessing their maturity, ownership and application potential.

The dissemination plan can include:

Publication of 1 open-access journal article (preferably in Q1/Q2 journals indexed in Scopus/Web of Science).

Development of a Handbook on Tourism Data Spaces, consolidating methodologies and lessons learned.

Produce **≥1 peer-reviewed article** on tourism data spaces, covering governance models, technical architecture.

Press and or Academic Release of 2 FAIR-compliant datasets/catalogues in open repositories.

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Organisation of a flagship Seminar on Tourism Data Spaces (TDS 2027), potentially during the DEPLOYTOUR’s final event.
Annual participation in major Data Space conferences to maintain visibility.
Ensuring all outputs are CC-BY 4.0 licensed, registered in **Zenodo/OpenAIRE**, and linked to KPIs on the project website.

Scientific contributions will involve all five universities as lead authors, with industrial co-authors on at least 75% of publications to ensure a balance of academic and industry perspectives.

All this content will be drafted in close collaboration with WP2, WP3, and WP4 to be aligned with the project outputs.

Monthly follow-up meetings will be organised to:

- Monitor progress
- Address challenges
- Align timelines
- Foster collaboration among institutions and disciplines

Overall research coordination will be led by the Universitat de les Illes Balears (UIB), overseeing planning, tracking, and progress across all dissemination activities. All publications will acknowledge DEPLOYTOUR, including the project title, funding programme (DIGITAL-2023-CLOUD-DATA-AI-05), and grant agreement number, in compliance with European Commission guidelines.

This exploitation activity will adopt a mixed-methods approach, combining qualitative and quantitative methodologies tailored to each output:

- **Technical papers:** Focus on architecture design, system modelling, benchmarking, and performance analysis.
- **Governance-related outputs:** Integrate policy analysis, stakeholder interviews, and regulatory framework reviews.
- **Pilot-based studies:** Utilise empirical fieldwork from project deployments across tourism destinations.
- **Co-creation workshops:** Engage partners and stakeholders to refine models and ensure real-world relevance iteratively.

This integrative methodology ensures that scientific contributions are both analytically rigorous and operationally grounded.

5.2 External training programme

The external training programme supports the WP6 objectives by:

- Raising awareness of data and data spaces in tourism.
- Equipping stakeholders with practical knowledge to participate in and benefit from the European Tourism Data Space (ETDS).
- Engaging data consumers and providers.
- Informing and educating stakeholders on the value of data-sharing.

The programme will target:

Tourism SMEs: Understand the benefits of joining data spaces, how to share data, and how to use shared data for business growth.

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DMOs: Understand the benefits of joining data spaces, access and use tourism data for destination management, planning, benchmarking and strategy definition and sustainability tracking.

Public Institutions: Understand the benefits of joining data spaces, learn governance models, interoperability frameworks, and how to support local data ecosystems.

Data Providers: Understand technical standards, data interoperability, data sovereignty, and the value creation process.

Data Consumers: Learn to access and use ETDS data to enhance services, product development, and decision-making.

An external training programme is essential to:

Unifying Visions and Terminology: Ensures engineers, legal officers, data stewards, and destination managers share a common language.

Building a Critical Mass of Trainers ensures rapid knowledge dissemination within organisations and to new member regions post-project.

Anchoring Sustainability: University-accredited courses and open-access MOOCs foster a living learning community, enabling future projects to build upon a recognised skill framework.

Both the platform and training programme will be validated with real users to ensure they meet actual needs. This external training will be delivered through university-validated courses with peer-learning dynamics and could offer a diploma.

Training is not just a support activity, but a central exploitation mechanism that translates project outputs into real-world capacities.

The methodology, tools, training structure, and timeline will begin development in Month 12 (M12).

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6. Conclusion

The first year of DEPLOYTOUR's communication and dissemination activities has set a positive foundation, supported by a realistic and actionable plan. The project has successfully entered its awareness phase, ensuring visibility among key stakeholders and building recognition of the DEPLOYTOUR brand.

However, for communication to be truly effective, particular attention must be paid to the quality and coherence of messages, ensuring that editorial content is directly connected to the project's concrete achievements.

The next phase of communication will depend on the progress and results delivered across the project's work packages, particularly through the pilots and technical developments. This highlights the need for strong synergies between WP6 and the other WPs to ensure that communication not only promotes DEPLOYTOUR but also clearly showcases its added value, results, and impact in a compelling manner.

By maintaining this alignment, DEPLOYTOUR will be able to amplify its reach, strengthen stakeholder engagement, and ensure long-term visibility and adoption of its outcomes.

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7. Annex

Annex 1: DEPLOYTOUR Target Groups

DEPLOYTOUR Target Groups	Example of Stakeholders	Main Message to raise awareness and attract target groups	Channels
EU decision makers, local and public authorities	European Commission DG Grow DG Connect HaDEA National ministries National agencies	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Creation of a roadmap and design principles towards the EU Data Spaces: deploying a robust technical infrastructure and governance mechanisms, aligning with the European data spaces Technical Framework and leveraging the insights gained from the preparatory actions. - Demonstrating the value proposition of data spaces in a specific sector: data sovereignty, usage control, better discovery, flow of quality data, and data security - Increasing the tourism sector's competitiveness. - Deployment of innovative services and applications through the five real-life use cases. - Cross-border data sharing 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Events Reports Public Deliverables Press releases Social Media Website Deck
Business and operational stakeholders in the field of Tourism	Data users Data providers From the tourism sector (SMEs, big companies)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Deploying a technical infrastructure and governance mechanisms, ensuring secure and controlled access to tourism data: providing the tools and governance mechanisms for trusted environments to mitigate current risks in data sharing and optimising processes and developing. - Data accessibility through 5 use cases: facilitate access to a large amount of accurate and reliable data. - Best practices from real-world data space implementations: feedback to further evolve common frameworks and standards, based on five pilots across Europe and networking potential for data sharing, interoperability and upscaling of project results for exploitation, transfer of knowledge. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Public Deliverables Newsletter Press releases Events Articles Social Media Website

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		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Ecosystem development: Collaboration with both public and private actors in European countries. - European cooperation - Innovative services and applications Supporting sustainable actions for tourism through technologies, understanding, and learning from the pain points and opportunities developed in the project's use cases. - Increasing the competitiveness 	
<p>Functional and technology stakeholders (implementation enablers)</p> <p>Data Spaces communities</p>	<p>Consulting companies Tech companies Tech providers (not specifically in the tourism sector)</p> <p>IDSA, GAIA-X, DSSC, FIWARE</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Deploying a common technical infrastructure and governance mechanisms: deployment of a common technical infrastructure, to meet the requirements of use cases and align with the emerging European data spaces technical framework, DSSC, SIMPL, and the preparatory actions. - Interoperability: the objective is to reach KPIs that include ensuring the interoperability of the common technical infrastructure. - Data accessibility through 5 use cases: facilitate access to a large amount of accurate and reliable data. - Opportunity to participate in data space technical groups or to stay informed about the project's progress. 	<p>Webinar Event Newsletter Article Social Media Website</p>
<p>General public and media</p>		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Positive impact on tourism experiences: DEPLOYTOUR contributes to the development of innovative services and applications, demonstrating their potential through real-life use cases. - Discovering data space: DEPLOYTOUR facilitates seamless access to and sharing of data, focusing on creating a secure, privacy-conscious data space with fine-tuned usage controls. This approach addresses concerns around data sharing, 	<p>Press Release Press kit Webinar Social Media Website</p>

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		<p>particularly in B2B and G2B contexts. By enabling robust data ecosystems, the project supports the advancement of sustainable and smart tourism strategies.</p> <p>Collaborative ecosystem: DEPLOYTOUR is committed to fostering collaboration among data providers and users, encompassing public and private actors across European countries. This cooperative approach is key in shaping the future of tourism data sharing.</p>	
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Annex 2: Events attended

Month	EVENT Name	CITY/ONLINE	DATE	WEBSITE	IF ORGANIZED BY ONE OF THE PARTNERS	PARTNERS PARTICIPATING
2024						
September	Towards a Smart Tourism	Online	September 30, 2024			ANYSOLUTION
October	European Big Data Value Forum (EBDVF)	Hungary, Budapest	October 2-4, 2024	https://european-big-data-value-forum.eu/		ANYSOLUTION, ITI, TECNALIA
	Nasa Space Apps Challenge	Vienna, Austria	October 5-6, 2024	https://www.spaceappschallenge.org/nasa-space-apps-2024/		ARCTUR
	EUSPA's User Consultation Platform (UCP)	Online	October 8, 2024	https://www.euspa-ucp.eu/		ANYSOLUTION
	Bridges for Cities	Vienna, Austria	October 10, 2024	https://www.unido.org/bridge-for-cities		ARCTUR
	Stakeholder Event	Brussels, Belgium	October 14, 2024	https://single-market-economy.ec.europa.eu/events/tourism-		ANYSOLUTION, EONA-X
	City DNA conference	Bruges, Belgium	October 15-18, 2024	https://citydestinationsalliance.eu/event/g	CityDNA	ANYSOLUTION, CityDNA, DATA APPEAL CO
	Tourism Innovation Summit (TIS)	Sevilla, Spain	October 23-25, 2024	https://www.tisglobalsummit.com/		ANYSOLUTION, EONA-X, DATA APPEAL CO
	Innovation in Tourist Destinations	online/Azores	November 1, 2024			ARCTUR
	ADR Forum	Eindhoven, Netherlands	November 4-5, 2024	https://adrforum.eu/		ITI

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November	World Travel Market (WTM)	London, England	November 5-7, 2024			
	Smart City World Congress (SCWC)	Barcelona, Spain	November 20-22, 2024	https://www.smartcityexpo.com/		ANYSOLUTION, AMADEUS SAS
	Equiphotel	Paris, France	November 3-7, 2024	https://www.equiphotel.com/en-gb.html#/		
	Global Data Spaces Connect 2024	Vienna, Austria	November 11, 2024	https://global-data-spaces-connect.com/		ARCTUR
	European Tourism Forum	Budapest, Hungary	November 12-14, 2024	https://hungarian-presidency.consilium.europa.eu/en/events		ANYSOLUTION
	Global Data Spaces Connect	Vienna, Austria	November 13, 2024	https://internationaldataspaces.org/event	IDSA	EONA-X, ARCTUR, AUSTRIA TOURISM, TECNALIA
	Gaia-X Summit 2024	Helsinki, Finland	November 15, 2024	https://gaia-x.eu/event/gaia-x-summit-2024-empowering-glo		EONA-X, ITI, TECNALIA
	Days of Slovene Tourism	Laško, Slovenia	November 18-19, 2024	https://www.slovenia.info/dnevi-slovenskega-turizma-2024		ARCTUR
	Sun&Blue Congress	Almeria, Spain	November 21-22, 2024	https://sunandbluecongress.com/en		ANYSOLUTION
	Europeana Project Week	Online	November 25-29, 2024	https://pro.europeana.eu/event/heritage-	STICHTING EUROPEANA	ANYSOLUTION
	Webinar: "Unlocking the Power of Data to Shape the Future of Travel"	Online	November 28, 2024			ANYSOLUTION
	EDIH Network Summer	Brussels, Belgium	November 26-27, 2024			ANYSOLUTION, ITI
	Buy Tourism Online (BTO)	Florence, Italy	November 27-28, 2024			
	IDSA Ecosystem Building Call	Online	December 2			ANYSOLUTION

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December	Cumbre Espacios de datos Gaia-X España	Madrid, Spain	December 03-04, 2024	https://www.gaiax-spain.com/primera-cumbre-de-espacios-d		ANYSOLUTION, TECNALIA, ITI, GMV-SGI, EONA-X
	Workshop “Shaping Tomorrow’s Tourism Today: The Power of AI Begins here”	Online	December03, 2024	https://www.unwto.org/europe/workshop	UN Tourism	
	Event ‘Technology and Data for DTI’	Online	December 06, 2024 (TBC)	Inicio - RED IBEROAMERICANA DE DESTINOS TURÍSTICOS INTELIGENTES		ANYSOLUTION
	Data Week	Luxembourg	December10, 2024	https://data-week.eu/	Big Data Value Association (BDV)	
	BEFUTURE	Paris, France	December11, 2024	https://www.linkeus.fr/befuture-innovation-hub-paris/		EONA-X
	Citiverse EDIC General Assembly	Valencia, Spain	December12, 2024	https://www.valencia.es/web/smartcity/eng/edic-ldt-general-		ITI
	Pleiades Member Showcase Event	Athens, Greece	December17, 2024	https://medium.com/@pleiadesIoTInnova	Pleiades IoT Innovation Cluster	PLEIAD
2025						
	FITUR	Madrid, Spain	January 22-26, 2025	https://www.ifema.es/fitur		TECNALIA, ANYSOLUTION, HIBERUSTEC, ITI
	CityDNA CEO meeting	Monaco	January 27-28, 2025	https://citydestinationsalliance.eu/event/a	CityDNA	CityDNA
January	SIMPL Annual Event	Brussels, Belgium	January 30, 2025	https://simpl-programme.ec.europa.eu/event/simpl-annual-e		ITI, TECNALIA, EONA-X
	Workshop for the initial validation of the OpenVerse	Online	January 21, 2025			ANYSOLUTION

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	Technological Framework for building European Virtual Worlds			Staff Working Document: information, insights and market trends		
	Travel Innovation Day 2025	Milan, Italy	January 30, 2025	https://www.osservatori.net/convegno/tra	POLITECNICO DI MILANO	POLITECNICO DI MILANO
February	BIT Milano	Milan, Italy	February 02-09			DATA APPEAL CO
	DSBC Data sharing festival	The Hague, Netherlands	February 4-5, 2025	https://internationaldataspaces.org/data-sharing-festival/		
	ENTER25 eTourism conference	Wrocław, Poland	February 17-21	ENTER25 - Welcome to IFITT		
	D3HUB Meeting		February 24-25, 2025			
	BTM Italia		February 26 - 28, 2025	https://www.btmitalia.it/it/signup		
March	TSI22 in-presence workshop output 2	Rome, Italy	March 4-5, 2025		MINISTERO DEL TURISMO	CityDNA
	ITB Berlin	Berlin, Germany	March 4-6, 2025	https://www.itb.com/en/		
	Guest lecture at Gea College	Ljubljana	Marzo 5, 2025			ARCTUR
	EU Sustainable Tourism workshop - Smart Solutions	Brussels, Belgium	March 11-12, 2025	https://single-market-economy.ec.europa.e		
	Data Spaces Symposium	Warsaw, Poland	March 11-12, 2025	https://www.data-spaces-symposium.eu/		

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						STICHTING EUROPEANA, NTT DATA SPAIN
	O futuro do Turismo	Brazil	March 18, 2025			ANYSOLUTION
	EU Sustainable Tourism workshop - Smart Solutions	Brussels, Belgium	March 26-27, 2025	https://single-market-economy.ec.europa.e	INTELLERA	INTELLERA
	Food Hotel Tech	France, Paris	March 19-20, 2025	https://www.foodhoteltech.com/en/		EONA-X
	Artificial Intelligence Algarve	Algarve, Portugal	March 20, 2025	https://www.meetup.com/grow-algarve-meetup/events/306257		UNL
April	Beyond Conference	Athens, Greece	April 4-6	https://www.beyond-expo.gr/	PLEIAD	PLEIAD
	Smart Destination Day 2025	Florence, Italy + Online	April 7, 2025		POLITECNICO DI MILANO, DATA APPEAL CO	POLITECNICO DI MILANO, DATA APPEAL CO, ANYSOLUTION
	CityDNA International Conference & General Assembly	Budapest, Hungary	April 9-11, 2025	https://citydestinationsalliance.eu/event/c	CityDNA	CityDNA, DATA APPEAL CO
	IDSA Event: Data spaces for industry event	Germany, Hannover	April 2, 2025			
	EU Sustainable Tourism workshop - Smart Solutions	Brussels, Belgium	April 8-9, 2025	https://single-market-economy.ec.europa.e	INTELLERA	INTELLERA
	“Conversas up” initiative, City Council	Alcochete, Portugal	April 10, 2025			UNL
	Ekoforum Herceg Novi	GHerceg Novi, Monte	April 9 to 11, 2025			ARCTUR

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				https://www.vozimnastrujuevent.com/		
	Open webinar - Interministerial Committee (WP5)	online	16/04/2025			
	Ibiza Tech Forum	Ibiza, Spain	April 22-25	https://ibizatechforum.com/		ANYSOLUTION
May	Vienna Up	Austria, Vienna	May 8 - 16, 2025	https://viennaup.com/		AUSTRIA TOURISM
	DEPLOYTOUR webinar: DEPLOYTOUR Beyond Borders: Tourism, Data & Cultural Heritage	Online	May 7, 2025	https://us06web.zoom.us/meeting/registre	ANYSOLUTION, EPGTDA SA, TECNALIA	
	EU Data & AI Summit	France, Paris	May 13, 2025		EONA-X	
	Digital Storytelling Festival 2025	online	May 13	https://europeana.zohobackstage.eu/DSF2	STICHTING EUROPEANA	ARCTUR
	GAIA-X Market-X & Expo / Tech-X & Hackathon #8	Spain, Valencia	May 13-14 2025	https://gaia-x.eu/market-x-tech-x-2025-agenda/		ANYSOLUTION, TECNALIA, ITI
	New Capabilities and Countries in European Space Conference	Rome, Italy	May 14-15	https://nikal.eventsair.com/new-capabilities-and-countries-in		ARCTUR
	Data2sustain Digital- driven Sustainable Tourism	Online	May 28; 2025	https://data2sustain.ie/event/digital-driven-sustainable-touri		ANYSOLUTION

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	IMEX	Frankfurt, Germany	May 22-25 2025			CityDNA
	NECSTouR Annual General Meeting	Milan, Italy	May 20-22 2025	https://www.regione.lombardia.it/wps/por	NECSTOUR	POLITECNICO DI MILANO
	Data Week	Athens, Greece	May 27-28, 2025	https://data-week.eu/		ANYSOLUTION, POLITECNICO DI MILANO, NTT DATA SPAIN, UNL, ITI
	European Tourism Day Tourism Stakeholders event	Brussels, Belgium	May 27, 2025	https://transition-pathways.europa.eu/news/dive-future-eu-t		ANYSOLUTION
	MyT Summit	Palma, Spain	May 29, 2025	https://www.mytsummit.com/		ANYSOLUTION
June	AMETIC Digital Tourist 2025	Benidorm, Spain	June 5-6, 2025	https://www.ametic-digital-tourist.es/		TECNALIA
	Destinations Exchange Europe	London, England	June 2, 2025	https://www.etoa.org/events/dee/		ANYSOLUTION, CityDNA, TURIZEM BOHINJ, DATA APPEAL CO
	INE Madrid	Madrid, Spain	June 9-10, 2025	https://turismo.csic.es/#		ANYSOLUTION
	Resilient Tourism Flagship Conference	Switzerland, Lucerne				
	Viva Technology	France, Paris	June 11-14, 2025			EONA-X
	Europeana annual conference	Warsaw, Poland	June 11-12, 2025	https://pro.europeana.eu/page/conferenc	STICHTING EUROPEANA	ANYSOLUTION
	Gaia-X Tourism Data Space Event	Online	June 18, 2025	https://gaia-x.eu/event/gaia-x-tourism-data-space-event/		ANYSOLUTION, EONA-X

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	Sustainable EU Tourism Webinar: Unlocking EU funding for sustainable and resilient tourism	Online	June 4th, 2025	https://events.teams.microsoft.com/event/1	INTELLERA	ANYSOLUTION
	Sustainable EU Tourism Webinar: Building capacity and fostering cooperation in tourism	Online	June 16th, 2025	https://events.teams.microsoft.com/event/2	INTELLERA	ANYSOLUTION
	AI Forum on Tourism and Smart Cities	Valencia, Spain	June 25th, 2025			ANYSOLUTION
	Andalucia x Nexus	Malaga, Spain	June 24th, 2025		TURESPAÑA	ANYSOLUTION; TURESPAÑA
	Sustainable EU Tourism Webinar: Practical tools for sustainable and resilient tourism through twinning and cooperation	Online	June 30th, 2025	https://events.teams.microsoft.com/event/b	INTELLERA	ANYSOLUTION
July	Implementation Dialogue on Data Policy	Brussels, Belgium	July 1st, 2025	https://commission.europa.eu/implementation-dialogues/imple		ANYSOLUTION
	Gaia-X Hub Germany	Online	July 10 th , 2025	https://events.teams.microsoft.com/event/a156edb1-6fca-4be		ANYSOLUTION
	Seminar: Artificial Intelligence and Tourism in the Americas	Hotel Westin Lima, Perú	July 31, 2025	https://www.unwto.org/events/70-cam-seminar-iai-and-tourism		ANYSOLUTION

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	Online webinar to present the high-level meeting	Online	July 28, 2025		Interministerial Committee	
August	2.º Foro de Tendencias en el Turismo	Centro Empresarial El Poblado – Cámara de comercio de Medellín para Antioquia	August 26-27	https://conectadosparacrecer.camamedellin.com.co/index/e		ANYSOLUTION
September	Meetings in Buenos Aires	Buenos Aires, Argentina	September 1-3			ANYSOLUTION
	Foro nacional de turismo	San Juan, Argentina	September, 4-5	https://foronacionaldeturismo2025.com/		ANYSOLUTION
	TourMIS workshop	Vienna	September 11-12	https://www.modul.ac.at/about/about-m	CityDNA	MODUL
	Data. Europa Academy webinar, 'Data spaces: experience from the European Tourism Data Space'	Online	September 12			ANYSOLUTION, EONA, PLEIAD
	Sumamoos technical event	Valencia	September 25			ANYSOLUTION
	CityDNA Autumn conference	Torshavn, Faroe Islands	September 30, October 2 2025		CityDNA	
	Urban Mobility Days	Vilnius, Lithuania	September 30, October 2 2025	https://transport.ec.europa.eu/news-events/main-events/urban		ANYSOLUTION

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	Smart Convention	Country Berlin, Germany	September 30, October 2 2025		
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Annex 3: Newsletters, articles, blogs and podcasts across partners

Partners	Related Activity	If not related to an activity, please specify	Type of Media (newspaper, blog, newsletter, website article)	Name of the article	Name of the Media (newspaper, blog, newsletter, website)	Date of publication	Link	Reach of people (if possible)
AMADEUS SAS	General information	Stakeholder forum	Article on my organisation website	Stakeholder forum: Exciting times ahead!	Viva Engage!	04/06/2025		80
ARCTUR	Kick-Off Meeting		Article on my organisation website	DEPLOYTOUR kick-off	Tourism4.0 Website	11/4/2024	https://tourism4-0.org/deploytour-kick-off/	
ARCTUR	General information		My organisation Newsletter	DEPLOYTOUR Kick-off	Tourism 4.0 Newsletter slo	12/9/2024		470
ARCTUR	General information		My organisation Newsletter	DEPLOYTOUR Kick-off	Tourism 4.0 Newsletter Eng	12/9/2024		260
ARCTUR	General information		My organisation Newsletter	DEPLOYTOUR Kick-off	Tourism 4.0 Newsletter LN edition	12/9/2024		800
ARCTUR	General information		Article on my organisation website	DEPLOYTOUR: establishing a common European data space for tourism	Arctur website	4/11/2024	https://www.arctur.si/en/rd-projects/deploytour/deploytour-vzpostavitev-skupnega-evropskega-podatkovnega-prostora-za-turizem-2024110414583915395/	
ARCTUR	Kick-Off Meeting		Article on my organisation website	DEPLOYTOUR: Five real-world use cases to deploy a Common European Tourism Data Space	Arctur website	6/11/2024	https://www.arctur.si/en/rd-projects/deploytour/deploytour-five-real-world-use-cases-to-deploy-a-common-european-tourism-data-space/	
ARCTUR	General information		Article on my organisation website	Harnessing AI and Data Analytics to Transform European Tourism	Tourism 4.0 website	3/10/2025	https://tourism4-0.org/deploytour-harnessing-ai-and-data-analytics-to-transform-european-tourism/	

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ARCTUR	General information		Article on my organisation's website	Harnessing AI and Data Analytics to Transform European Tourism	Arctur website	3/10/2025	https://www.arctur.si/en/rd-projects/deploytour/harnessing-ai-and-data-analytics-to-transform-european-tourism/	
ARCTUR	General information		Article on my organisation website	DEPLOYTOUR kick-off	Tourism 4.0 website	6/11/2024	https://tourism4-0.org/deploytour-kick-off/	
ARCTUR	WP4_Use Case in general		My organisation Newsletter	Ecoforum and pilots	Tourism 4.0 Newsletter slo	5/22/2025	https://mailchi.mp/e59b0428986f/turizem-40-pomladne-novice-2025	
ARCTUR	WP4_Use Case in general		My organisation Newsletter	Ecoforum and pilots	Tourism 4.0 Newsletter Eng	5/22/2025	https://mailchi.mp/e59b0428986f/turizem-40-pomladne-novice-2025	
ARCTUR	WP4_Use Case in general		My organisation Newsletter	Ecoforum and pilots	Tourism 4.0 Newsletter LN edition	5/22/2025	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7331205575709507584	
AUSTRIA TOURISM	General information		Article on my organisation website	Data Bites #2: DEPLOYTOUR - Jonathan Huffstutler	CTA	01/02/2025	https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=CgPkd0ns8DQ&feature=youtu.be	
CityDNA	Kick-Off Meeting		Article on my organisation website	DEPLOYTOUR: Five real-world use cases to deploy a Common European Tourism Data	City DNA website	11/13/2024	https://citydestinationsalliance.eu/deploytour-five-real-world-use-cases-to-deploy-a-common-european-tourism-data-space/	
CityDNA	General information	#1 DEPLOYTOUR Newsletter	My organisation Newsletter		City DNA Newsletter	12/20/2024		1374
DATA APPEAL CO	General information		Podcast	Tutto quello che devi sapere sul Progetto Deploytour	Data Appeal Byte-Sized Trends - EXPERT TALK	24/06/2025	https://datappeal.io/it/podcast/	103
EONA-X	Kick-Off Meeting		My organisation Newsletter	Lancement du projet européen DEPLOYTOUR	EONA-X Newsletter	11/18/2024		66

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EONA-X	General information		My organisation Newsletter	Collaborating in the DEPLOYTOUR European Project	EONA-X Newsletter	2/20/2025		83
EONA-X	General information		My organisation Newsletter			5/23/2025		104
EONA-X	General information	Stakeholder forum	My organisation Newsletter			01/07/2025	https://csxhc.r.sp1-brevo.net/mk/mr/sh/6rqJ8GoudeITQXmW6YIL4eG7fst/zC0Hf-zyWWZf	119
FRAUNHOFER	General information		Article on my organisation website	DEPLOYTOUR: Einführung eines vertrauenswürdigen und sicheren gemeinsamen europäischen Tourismusdatenumms	Fraunhofer ISST Website	5/9/2025	https://www.isst.fraunhofer.de/de/abteilungen/mobility-und-smart-cities/projekte/DEPLOYTOUR.html	
FRAUNHOFER	General information		Podcast	Mehr Datenqualität für besseres Reisen - Wie Daten den Tourismus resilienter und nachhaltiger machen	Die Datenräume	31/07/2025	https://open.spotify.com/episode/6boOcCMi7xNCJ47t5B5Ka5?si=d711183c0fb84a22	300
HIBERUSTEC	General information	Internal Newsletter	My organisation Newsletter			12/1/2024		
ITI	Partners' Meeting		Article on my organisation website	ITI participa en la primera reunión plenaria de DEPLOYTOUR celebrada en París	ITI Website	16/05/2025	https://www.iti.es/noticias/iti-participa-en-la-primera-reunion-plenaria-de-deploytour-celebrada-en-paris/	
ITI	General information		Article on my organisation website	ITI participa en un proyecto europeo de 15,3 millones de euros para	ITI Website	29/07/2025	https://www.iti.es/noticias/iti-participa-en-un-proyecto-europeo-de-153-millones-de-	

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				digitalizar y conectar destinos turísticos			euros-para-digitalizar-y-conectar-destinos-turisticos/	
LAPLAND UAS	Kick-Off Meeting		Article on my organisation website	DEPLOYTOUR: Viisi reaailmaailman käyttötapausta yhteisen eurooppalaisen matkailun data-avaruuden käyttöönotossa	Lapland UAS website	11/07/2024	Viisi reaailmaailman käyttötapausta yhteisen eurooppalaisen matkailun data-avaruuden käyttöönotossa	
LAPLAND UAS	General information	Also kick off meeting	My organisation Newsletter	DEPLOYTOUR – Deployment of a trusted and secure Common European Tourism Data Space	LUC Research and Development Newsletter	12/11/2024		
LIBELIUM	General information		Article on my organisation website	The Map of Data Spaces for Environmental Sustainability	Libelium website	16/07/2025	https://www.libelium.com/libeliuworld/the-map-of-data-spaces-for-environmental-sustainability/?utm_source=linkedin&utm_medium=social_organicc&utm_campaign=positive_tech_map_dataspaces	
MINISTERO DEL TURISMO	General information		Article on my organisation website	DEPLOYTOUR: il Ministero del Turismo partecipa al progetto europeo per la trasformazione digitale del settore turistico	Ministero del Turismo website	10/01/2025	news sul sito	
NTT DATA SPAIN	Link to DEPLOYTOUR website	General information	Internal communication channel		R&D External Funding community			

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NTT SPAIN	DATA	Kick-Off Meeting	Also general information	Internal communication channels	Leading the technological transformation of the tourism sector	NTT DATA connect / R&D External Funding community	12/10/24		73
NTT SPAIN	DATA	Participation in Events	DEPLOYTOUR at FITUR	Internal communication channels	NTT DATA apuesta por la innovación digital en el sector turístico	NTT DATA connect / R&D External Funding community	11/06/2025		29
PLEIAD		General information		My organisation Newsletter	October Newsletter	Newsletter	11/07/2024	https://mailchi.mp/fab0c42801ee/pleiades-newsletter-october?e=e072f9fe90	
PLEIAD		Kick-Off Meeting		Newsletter of my local partners	DEPLOYTOUR	Pleiades Monthly Newsletter	5/12/24	https://mailchi.mp/4f4309eae26/pleiades-newsletter-november	
PLEIAD		Participation in Events		Article on my organisation website	Pleiades Member Showcase in Athens: Connecting Our Greek Innovation Ecosystem	Website	14/01/2024	https://www.google.com/url?q=https://medium.com/@pleiadesloTInnovationCluster/pleiades-member-showcase-in-athens-connecting-the-greek-innovation-ecosystem-53c23607d28e&sa=D&source=docs&ust=1754385686729273&u sg=AOvVaw3KhOa8ZWCpBVf0Asvxo4xi	
PLEIAD		Participation in Events		Article on my organisation website	Pleiades Pavilion at BEYOND Expo 2025: A Space for Innovation and Collaboration	Website	24/03/2025	https://medium.com/@pleiadesloTInnovationCluster/pleiades-pavilion-beyond-expo-2025-de41f7ba283e	
PLEXUS		Kick-Off Meeting		Article on my organisation website	DEPLOYTOUR: 5 proyectos piloto para un Espacio de Datos de Turismo Europeo Común	Plexus Tech News	11/07/2024	DEPLOYTOUR: 5 proyectos para un Espacio de Datos de Turismo Europeo Común	
STICHTING EUROPEANA		General information		Article on my organisation's website	DEPLOYTOUR	Europeana Pro website	10/1/2024	https://pro.europeana.eu/project/deploytour	800

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STICHTING EUROPEANA	Kick-Off Meeting		Article on my organisation website	Europeana to help build the Common European Tourism Data Space	Europeana Pro website	11/20/2024	https://pro.europeana.eu/post/europeana-to-help-build-the-common-european-tourism-data-space	200
STICHTING EUROPEANA	Kick-Off Meeting		My organisation Newsletter	Europeana to help build the Common European Tourism Data Space	ENA Newsletter	06/12/24	https://fdti-zcmp.campaign-view.eu/ua/viewinbrowser?od=3zf064725ec845c9b06767fb858765cc8d&rd=119ffc119555a3&sd=119ffc11954299&n=124296dfe4fabb&mrd=119ffc11954287&m=1	4,300
STICHTING EUROPEANA	General information		Article on my organisation website	Europeana Foundation Business Plan 2025	Europeana Pro website	01/16/2025	https://pro.europeana.eu/post/europeana-foundation-business-plan-2025	
STICHTING EUROPEANA	General information		Article on my organisation website	The Europeana Initiative wishes you a happy New Year 2025	Europeana Pro website	01/16/2025	https://pro.europeana.eu/post/the-europeana-initiative-wishes-you-a-happy-new-year-2025	
STICHTING EUROPEANA	General information		Article on my organisation website	Europeana partners with X. Design Week to advance cultural heritage and tourism	Europeana Pro website	05/21/2025	https://pro.europeana.eu/post/europeana-partners-with-x-design-week-to-advance-cultural-heritage-and-tourism	
TRENITALIA	General information		Internal communication channels	Mobility data sharing for sustainable tourism reasons	Trenitalia Open Lab Weekly Meeting	11/27/2024		30
TRENITALIA	WP4_Use Case 1		Internal communication channels	SAL Progetti Europeri: Deploy tour	Trenitalia Open Lab Weekly Meeting	2/5/2025		40
UIB	General information		Article on my organisation website	La UIB participa en un projecte per desplegar un espai	Diari de la UIB	26/06/2025	https://diari.uib.es/Hemeroteca/La-UIB-participa-en-un-projecte-per-desplegar-un.cid808109	

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Annex 4: Media exposure at local, national and European levels

Partners	Related Activity	If not related to an activity, please specify	Type of Media (newspaper, blog, newsletter, website article)	Name of the article	Name of the Media (newspaper, blog, newsletter, website)	Date of publication	Link	Reach of possible)
ANYSOLUTION	Kick-Off Meeting		Local newspaper	DEPLOYTOUR Kick Off Meeting	Local press Mallorca	10/31/2024		
ANYSOLUTION	General information		Local newspaper	Turismo, el equilibrio necesario	Local press Mallorca/ Diario de Mallorca	11/25/2024	https://www.linkedin.com/posts/anysolution_nota-de-prensa-activity-7267548465533014017-CmqB?utm_source=share&utm_medium=member_desktop&rcm=ACoAACAwBoB9dHxPHZ3QgWPaihV4FSNYIFPOQk	
ANYSOLUTION	General information	Governance	Whitepaper	Data Governance for Tourism Governance	Gaia-X Tourism Ecosystem	15/06/2025	https://gaia-x.eu/wp-content/uploads/2025/05/White-Paper-Data-Governance-for-Tourism-Governance.pdf	
ANYSOLUTION	General information		Blog	Creating a Data-Driven Future for Tourism: Building Sustainable, Resilient and Competitive Destinations	BDVA	6/13/2025	https://bdva.eu/blog/creating-a-data-driven-future-for-tourism/	
ANYSOLUTION	General information		Podcast	Data Space Podcast	Startin' Blox	21/07/2025	https://www.linkedin.com/posts/startinblox_dsp-6-matthias-buchhorn-roth-activity-7348313667030937600-RnZ2?utm_source=share&utm_medium=member_desktop&rcm=ACoAACAwBoB9dHxPHZ3QgWPaihV4FSNYIFPOQk	

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DEPLOYTOUR	General information	DEPLOYTOUR at the Tourism Innovation Summit	National newspaper	Tourism Innovation Summit	Tourism Innovation Summit newsletter	4/21/2025	https://mailing.nebext.com/view.html?x=a62e&co=6CTC&m=fvgov&mc=3&s=1qEDXT&u=wRwD4&z=yOX2ux5&	
DEPLOYTOUR	WP5_Synergies	Webinar: Tourism, Data & Mobility	European newspaper	European newspaper	EU Tourism Platform	04/08/2025	https://transition-pathways.europa.eu/events/webinar-deploytour-beyond-borders-tourism-data-mobility	
DeployEMDS	WP5_Synergies		Article on my organisation website	Save the Date: DEPLOYTOUR & deployEMDS Webinar on Tourism Data and Mobility	DeployEMDS	29/07/2025	Save the Date: DEPLOYTOUR & deployEMDS Webinar on Tourism Data and Mobility – deployEMDS	
DISSET	Kick-Off Meeting		Local newspaper	DEPLOYTOUR Kick Off Meeting	Local press Mallorca	10/31/2024		
DISSET	Kick-Off Meeting		Local newspaper	Una empresa mallorquina lidera un proyecto europeo de 15,3 millones	Local press Mallorca	4/11/2024	https://www.diariodemallorca.es/mallorca/2024/11/04/empresa-mallorquina-lidera-proyecto-europeo-111338213.html	2.096.208 unique
DISSET	Kick-Off Meeting		Local newspaper	Mallorca acoge el nacimiento del Espacio Europeo de Datos Turísticos	Local press Mallorca	4/11/2024	https://www.ultimahora.es/noticias/local/2024/11/04/2270075/mallorca-acoge-nacimiento-del-espacio-europeo-datos-turisticos.html	3.349.455 unique
DISSET	Kick-Off Meeting		Local newspaper	Deploytour: 5 proyectos piloto para desplegar un Espacio de Datos de Turismo Europeo Común	Local press Mallorca	4/11/2024	https://www.economiademallorca.com/articulo/turismo-y-hosteleria/deploytour-5-proyectos-piloto-desplegar-espacio-datos-turismo-europeo-comun/20241104200715100191.html	14.358 unique
DISSET	Kick-Off Meeting		Local newspaper	El consorcio DEPLOYTOUR	Local press Mallorca	4/11/2024	https://canal4diario.com/2024/11/05/el-consorcio-deploytour-	6390 unique

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				pretende «revolucionar el sector turístico» a base de compartir datos			pretende-revolucionar-el-sector-turistico-a-base-de-compartir-datos/	
EONA-X	WP4_Use Case 3		National newspaper	Open-data : quelles sont les ambitions de DEPLOYTOUR pour le Tourisme	Tom.travel	2/27/2025	https://www.tom.travel/2025/02/27/open-data-queelles-sont-les-ambitions-de-deploytour-pour-le-tourisme/	
EONA-X	General information		National newspaper	L'intelligence artificielle et l'accès aux données au service du tourisme et du transport	Les annales des Mines	01/07/2025	https://annales-des-mines.org/wp-content/uploads/2025/06/RE-2025-07-25-Lintelligence-artificielle-et-lacces-aux-donnees-au-service-du-tourisme-et-du-transport-C.-TELITSINE-et-J.-HUFFSTUTLER.pdf	
EONA-X	General information		National newspaper	EONA-X : « La donnée est une ressource stratégique pour le MICE »	Deplacements. pros	23/07/2025	https://www.deplacementspros.com/mice/eona-x-la-donnee-est-une-ressource-strategique-pour-le-mice	
EU Platform	Tourism	General information	European newspaper	DEPLOYTOUR: Driving digital transformation in European tourism	Tourism Transition Pathway Stakeholder Support Platform – Newsletter	10/31/2024	https://ec.europa.eu/newsroom/growth/newsletter-archives/57133	
EU Platform	Tourism	WP5_Synergies	European newspaper	DEPLOYTOUR webinar: Unlocking data's role in tourism and cultural heritage	EU Tourism Platform	21/07/2025	https://transition-pathways.europa.eu/event-resources/deploytour-webinar-unlocking-datas-role-tourism-and-cultural-heritage	
EU Platform	Tourism	WP5_Synergies	European newspaper	DEPLOYTOUR webinar: Exploring data	EU Tourism Platform	17/07/2025	https://transition-pathways.europa.eu/event-resources/deploytour-webinar-	

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				spaces in tourism and smart cities			exploring-data-spaces-tourism-and-smart-cities	
Fundació BIT (no partner)	General information		Local newspaper + Newsletter	La empresa mallorquina AnySolution lidera un proyecto europeo para digitalizar y conectar destinos turísticos	Diario de Mallorca	01/07/2025	https://www.linkedin.com/posts/fundaciobit_la-empresa-mallorquina-anysolution-lidera-activity-7356262076501098496-U7Rr?utm_source=share&utm_medium=member_desktop&rcm=ACoAACAwYBoB9dHxPHZ3QgWPaihV4FSNYIFPOQk	
ITI	WP4_Use Case 2		Local newspaper	DEPLOYTOUR, el proyecto europeo que digitaliza el turismo, liderado por España	MuyPymes	22/08/2025	https://www.muypymes.com/2025/08/21/deploytour-proyecto-europeo-digitaliza-turismo-liderado-espana	

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